
Quantifying the Saliency of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

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Abstract

Safe global deployment of AI models requires alignment with human values that vary across cultures. Yet rater pools in safety evaluation datasets remain largely geographically homogeneous, failing to capture geo-cultural differences. Further, it remains unclear whether such differences persist after controlling for demographics such as age, gender, and ethnicity. Through a meta-analysis of safety datasets, we find that most do not report geo-cultural information, and those that do lack a unified methodology to jointly analyze geo-cultural and demographic correlates. Using the Inglehart-Welzel dimensions of cross-cultural variation (Inglehart & Welzel, 2005), we demonstrate via multilevel modeling that cultural zone membership explains variance in safety ratings beyond standard demographics ($p < 0.05$ across 6 datasets). Moreover, our analysis indicates that roughly 10% of items in the datasets we examined are culturally sensitive: likely to be misclassified as safe without adequate cultural representation. We evaluate LLMs as both rater surrogates and triage tools, finding that current LLMs do not reliably stand in for raters, though they can help prioritize culturally sensitive items for human annotation. Our findings motivate more culturally pluralistic safety evaluation and offer practical takeaways to support it.

 [asaakyan/culture-safety](https://github.com/asaakyan/culture-safety)
 [asaakyan.github.io/culture-safety](https://github.com/asaakyan/culture-safety)

1. Introduction

Alignment of AI models to pluralistic human values remains a challenging yet crucial direction in AI safety (Sorensen et al., 2024; Mushkani et al., 2025). It is well established that

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perceptions of (AI-generated) content safety vary by user demographics, such as ethnicity, age, and gender (Kumar et al., 2021; Sap et al., 2022; Sachdeva et al., 2022; Rastogi et al., 2025; Petrova et al., 2026). More recently, studies have drawn attention to cultural value variation across countries (geo-cultural variation), observing misalignment between modern AI systems and global populations (Davani et al., 2024; Kirk et al., 2024; Durmus et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2025). Despite being a crucial aspect of alignment given the increasingly global deployment of AI systems, current work on AI safety largely ignores the question of cultural pluralism. Most datasets for safety and alignment via human feedback, e.g. RLHF (Ouyang et al., 2022), are typically geographically homogeneous (Bai et al., 2022a; Ganguli et al., 2022; Glaese et al., 2022), with notable exceptions such as the PRISM dataset (Kirk et al., 2024). As a result, models fine-tuned on such datasets run the risk of systematically producing harmful outputs for underrepresented user populations (Rastogi et al., 2026).

Prior quantitative AI safety studies have largely focused on diversifying human raters across demographics like gender, age and ethnicity, which may not be sufficient to qualify the underlying cultural value systems (Nice, 2024) (i.e. the shared normative frameworks that define what a society considers harmful). Only a few safety studies employ geo-cultural stratification (Davani et al., 2024; Lee et al., 2024), however they do not fully control for demographic confounds, or remain limited to just the text modality. Concurrently, AI alignment research has widely adopted automated alignment (LLM-as-a-Judge) approaches (Bai et al., 2022b; Inan et al., 2023; Gupta et al., 2024; Yuan et al., 2025; Jindal et al., 2025; Thomas et al., 2025). However, these methods rest on an unsubstantiated assumption that models can reliably simulate diverse human perspectives supported by standard rater attributes, such as demographics (Rastogi et al., 2025; Movva et al., 2024).

Thus, current AI safety methods demonstrate a considerable gap of understanding why, where, and how to attain alignment with geo-culturally diverse values. In this paper, we develop methodological frameworks to address why geo-cultural diversity is important for safety, providing concrete quantitative evidence; where or which data items are affected; and how data collection can be improved, including with LLM-in-the-loop methods. Our contributions are:

Figure 1. Geo-cultural diversity of raters in 8 safety datasets on the Inglehart-Welzel Cultural Map of the World. Each dot is a rater. Cultural zone names point to zone centroids, top 3 countries by annotator count and the number of raters are listed underneath.

- **A meta-analysis of the geo-cultural gap:** We conduct a systematic survey of existing safety datasets, revealing that only 8 contain both demographic and geo-cultural rater attributes (Sec. 3), illustrated in Figure 1.
- **Identifying geo-cultural salience:** Using multilevel modeling, we demonstrate that raters’ cultural zone is a significant predictor of safety ratings beyond standard demographics ($p < .05$ across six datasets, Sec. 4).
- **Quantifying geo-cultural blind spots:** We introduce a cultural sensitivity score (Sec. 5), revealing that culture-agnostic annotation would lead to a false negative rate of roughly 10% in the datasets we examined, labeling content that is unsafe for a specific cultural value quadrant as safe.
- **Opportunities and Limits of LLM automation:** Our experiments (Sec. 6) show that (1) fine-tuned and reasoning LMs are not reliable at emulating judgments of raters from diverse cultural backgrounds; (2) fine-tuned LMs can identify items where raters from different cultural backgrounds disagree on the safety judgment.

Conflict of Interest Disclosure. The authors CR, LA are employed by Google, which leads the development of Gemma and Gemini models, which were among the ones evaluated in this paper.

2. Related Work

Prior work on annotator disagreements has found that rater-specific behavior (Jiang et al., 2025; Orlikowski et al., 2025) or moral values (Davani et al., 2024) are more predictive of safety labels than aggregate demographics, but collecting individual values or stratifying across rater behaviors is costly and difficult to scale. Demographic stratification can still be a useful proxy for human label variation (Wan et al., 2023; Rastogi et al., 2025; Li et al., 2026; Petrova et al., 2026). Viewing disagreement as a meaningful signal rather than noise (Aroyo & Welty, 2015; Uma et al., 2022; Plank, 2022), we seek to reduce the complexity of additional rater stratification by cultural values in a theory-driven way.

Prior work on safety in the cultural context focuses on cultural knowledge (Chiu et al., 2025), cultural biases (Nayak et al., 2025) and understanding of socio-cultural norms (Qiu et al., 2025; Varimalla et al., 2025). Our analysis shows that culture is an important factor even in generic safety datasets that were not tailored to elicit cultural disagreement, such as DIVE (Rastogi et al., 2025) and PRISM (Kirk et al., 2024). We discuss such datasets in more detail in the next section.

3. Geo-Cultural Gap: Dataset Meta-Analysis

To understand the salience and past treatment of geo-cultural values, we searched for safety datasets containing geographic proxies (e.g., country of birth, nationality) as well as demographics (e.g. age, gender, ethnicity). We then

conducted a meta-analysis of qualifying datasets.

Dataset identification approach. We employed a snowballing strategy (Badampudi et al., 2015) to parse through citations of prominent safety dataset papers (e.g., DIVE (Rastogi et al., 2025), DICES (Aroyo et al., 2023), PRISM (Kirk et al., 2024)). Additionally, we searched abstracts and texts of major Natural Language Processing, Machine Learning, Computer Vision and Fairness venues (ACL, FAccT, AIES, NeurIPS, ICLR, ICML, ICCV, ECCV, CVPR) using the terms *culture*, *dataset* and *safety*, yielding 1062 candidate records. Surprisingly, only 8 studies met the criteria for inclusion, i.e. reporting both demographics and geo-cultural information associated with the ratings. This reveals a systemic lack of geo-cultural reporting in safety research.

Comparison of rater attribute documentation. In Table 1, we compare qualifying datasets by *modality* (e.g. text, text-to-image, text-to-text), *annotation task* (e.g., offensiveness detection, stereotype ratings), *descriptive statistics* (e.g. number of items and raters), and *demographic* and *geo-cultural attribute* coverage. In Figure 1, we visualize the geo-cultural diversity of surveyed datasets: visually, cultures with high Traditional, Self-expression and Secular, Survival values are underrepresented within the datasets.

Datasets varied by reporting and coverage of geographic attributes (country of birth, residence, nationality), which are widely used to study cultural differences (Inglehart & Welzel, 2005; Hofstede, 2001; Gelfand et al., 2011). Most datasets report either country of birth (CoB), residence (CoR), or nationality (CoN), with only two datasets reporting all three. Only three datasets cover more than 10 countries with at least one geo-cultural attribute (e.g., 10+ CoRs represented).

In terms of the standard demographic attributes, all datasets reported gender and age, and all but two reported ethnicity. The granularity of reporting varied across ethnicity (e.g., “Asian” vs. South/East Asian), gender (binary vs. non-binary), and age (age group vs. specific age). Socio-economic factors were not reported consistently, with only one dataset (D3) containing self-reported socio-economic status, while others reported a mix of education, employment, or neither. See Table 6 in Appendix for full demographic and cultural attribute comparison.

All datasets reported item identifying numbers (hereafter: ID) and rater ID information which allow to account for rater subjectivity and item severity. In the NLPositionality dataset, only session ID is reported, which might not correspond to a unique rater. Some datasets report additional rater and item attributes, such as raters’ LLM familiarity (e.g., very familiar) in PRISM or harm topic of the prompt-image pair (e.g., bias, violence) in DIVE.

Comparison of study design. D3, CREHate, DICES-990, and Severity adopted a crossed study design to ensure a balanced set of annotations per item from different countries. DIVE and NLPositionality (NLPos) did not purposefully balance by cultural background (e.g., in NLPos, 97% of the raters were part of a single cultural zone). CulturalFrames adopts a nested design, where raters from each culture rate their own set of items, and in PRISM each rater annotates a single unique item (their own conversation with a chatbot). Overall, no study stratifies by both cultural background and demographics (ethnicity, age, gender).

Operationalizing culture. Most datasets did not draw on theoretical frameworks to motivate the cultural composition of the rater pool. Those remaining either used Hofstede’s cultural dimensions (Hofstede, 2011) in auxiliary analyses (D3, CREHate), or the World Values Survey (WVS, Haerpfer et al., 2022) in the design of their recruitment strategy (CulturalFrames).

Analysis of rating disagreements. A key aspect of these studies is the analysis of disagreement between different rater populations. Most such analyses either considered only demographic (DIVE, DICES-990) or only geo-cultural (NLPos, CREHate, Severity) factors as a source of disagreement. Some studies conducted a limited analysis on both: PRISM analyzed conversation topic differences by rater location, but not safety ratings; D3 included demographic variables (gender, age, socio-economic status) only one at a time as fixed effects, rather than jointly.

As for the methods to analyze the differences, three studies (DIVE, DICES-990, NLPos) used IRR (inter-rater reliability)-based methods such as the Group Association Index (Prabhakaran et al., 2024). Two papers used statistical simulations to model ratings of various groups (PRISM, DIVE). Two studies relied on average or majority votes (CREHate, CulturalFrames). Regression methods such as multilevel regression (D3), linear regression with clustered standard errors (PRISM) and exponential regression (Severity) were also applied. Overall, only one paper relied on robust statistical methods such as multilevel regression to analyze the impact of culture on rater disagreement, and none accounted for all standard demographic attributes.

4. Geo-Cultural & Demographic Salience

Given these limitations, prior studies do not provide conclusive evidence of the importance of geo-cultural values, or the strength of their impact beyond demographic factors. We first estimate the impact of demographics and culture separately. Then, we estimate whether culture improves predictive power beyond demographics, as well as whether culture moderates the effects of demographics.

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Dataset	Modality	Annotation Task	Statistics				Demographics	Geo-Cultural Scope	Rater or Item Info
			#Annots	#Raters	#Items	Avg #Raters/Item			
DIVE (Rastogi et al., 2025)	T2I	Safety of T2I gen.	31.9K	636	1.0K	32	Age, Gender, Ethn.	CoR: UK, US CoB/CoN: 10+	item_id, rater_id, topic
CulturalFrames (Nayak et al., 2025)	T2I	Stereotype ratings	9.9K	379	3.5K	3	Age, Gender, Edu., Empl.	CoR/CoLR/CoB/CoN: 10+	rater_id, item_id, category, model
PRISM (Kirk et al., 2024)	T2T	Safety of conv. AI	7.5K	1.3K	7.5K	1	Age, Gender, Ethn., Edu., Emp., Marital	CoR/CoB: 10+	item_id, rater_id, llm familiarity, llm, llm provider
DICES-990 (Aroyo et al., 2023)	T2T	Safety of conv. AI	51.3K	119	990	52	Age, Gender, Ethn., Edu.	CoR: US, India	item_id, rater_id, phase, degree of harm, harm type
NLPos (Santy et al., 2023)	T	Hate speech	6.3K	505	299	18	Age, Gender, Ethn.	CoLR/CoR: 10+	item_id, rater_id
D3 (Davani et al., 2024)	T	Offensiveness	153.3K	4.3K	4.6K	30	Age, Gender, SES	CoR: 10+	item_id, rater_id, topic
CREHate (Lee et al., 2024)	T	Toxicity	41.7K	1K	1.6K	26	Age, Gender, Ethn., Edu., Sex. Or.	CoN: AU, UK, US, SG, SA	item_id, rater_id, data source
Severity (Jiang et al., 2021)	T	Severity of harmful topics	49.0K	1.4K	66	742	Age, Gender, Ethn., Edu.	CoR: BR, EG, IN, ID, PH, TR, US, VN	rater_id, item_id

Table 1. Comparison of safety datasets with geographically diverse raters based on modality (‘Mod’), volume, demographic coverage, and additional data about raters and items. Abbreviations: *CoR* (Country of Residence), *CoLR* (Country of Longest Residence), *CoB* (Country of Birth), *CoN* (Country of Nationality), SES (socio-economic status), Ethn. (ethnicity), Sex. Or. (sexual orientation), Edu. (education). *item_id*, *rater_id* refer to rater and item identifiers, respectively. Statistics are rounded off to the nearest 1000 (K) where relevant. Datasets are henceforth referred to by their name provided in the first column.

4.1. Methods

Operationalizing culture. To operationalize cultural value diversity, we draw on existing empirical measures (Zhao et al., 2024a). Prior work primarily used the World Values Survey (WVS) or Hofstede’s cultural dimensions (e.g., Masoud et al. (2025)). We turn to WVS, the most comprehensive longitudinal survey of values worldwide, which has been widely adopted for evaluating alignment and pluralistic cultural values (Arora et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2024b; Jiang et al., 2025; Liu et al., 2025; Adilazuarda et al., 2025; Kabir et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2025). In contrast, Hofstede’s measurements originated from a survey of IBM employees and have not been refreshed through comparable cross-national waves. Political scientists R. Inglehart and C. Welzel identified two key cultural value axes – Traditional-Secular and Survival-Self-Expression – explaining over 70% of cross-national variance in WVS responses (Inglehart & Welzel, 2005). Countries can be plotted along these axes and grouped into *cultural zones* on the Inglehart-Welzel (IW) cultural map (see Figure 4 in Appendix). These zones reflect shared values (as measured by recent WVS waves) and historical, economic, or religious context rather than geographic proximity (e.g., the “Latin America” zone includes both Guatemala and the Philippines). For experiments using the continuous cultural value axes directly, see Appendix C.2.

Current safety datasets do not report raters’ cultural self-identification, instead relying on geographical proxies such as country of longest residence (CoLR), birth (CoB), residence (CoR), or nationality (CoN). When multiple proxies are present, it is unclear which one to choose for cultural zone assignment. To address this, we use the following prioritization: CoLR or CoB is preferred over CoR; CoB is preferred over CoN. This ordering reflects two concerns. First, country of residence may reflect recent immigration without sufficient time for acculturation (Berry, 1997), so country of longest residence or birth is a better proxy. Second, raters may have multiple nationalities, reporting the one that yields the highest wages on crowd-working platforms (Kennedy et al., 2020), making nationality a less reliable proxy than birth. Empirically, we see additional support for this framework in experiments with PRISM, DIVE, and NLPos, see Appendix C.1.

Analysis of rater disagreements. IRR-based methods can tell whether certain groups agree with each other more than with other groups. However, such methods rely on bootstrapping for statistical robustness (Prabhakaran et al., 2024; Movva et al., 2024), requiring a large number of samples stratified by demographic and geo-cultural characteristics. Multilevel models have been proposed for rigorous analysis of group differences in safety annotations (Sachdeva et al., 2022; Homan et al., 2024; Davani et al., 2024; Jiang et al.,

2024; Petrova et al., 2026). Unlike IRR-based methods, multilevel models do not require stratified subsamples, instead jointly modeling variation across items, raters, and group-level characteristics (Gelman & Hill, 2007; Baayen et al., 2008; Yarkoni, 2022). Given limited replication within demographic and cultural strata, we employ multilevel modeling as a robust and broadly applicable method to estimate the impact of demographic and geo-cultural variables on label variation across all datasets surveyed in Section 3.

4.2. Culture is predictive of safety ratings

To answer whether geo-cultural background and demographics affect safety annotation, we fit multilevel logistic regressions for binary ratings and multilevel linear regressions for Likert-style ratings.¹ First, a *base model* is fit, accounting only for variation in items and raters as random effects. Any additional data about raters or items specific to each dataset (e.g., topic of the safety violation, see Rater or Item info columns in Table 1) was incorporated as a random effect, unless the number of levels was too low.² Formally, for Likert-style ratings:

$$H_{ij} = \beta_0 + u_i + v_j + \epsilon_{ij} \quad (1)$$

Here H_{ij} denotes the rating of rater i on item j , $u_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{rater}}^2)$ is the random effect for rater i , $v_j \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{item}}^2)$ is the random effect for item j , and $\epsilon_{ij} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\epsilon}^2)$ is the residual error.

Next, to understand whether demographic factors or cultural factors have predictive value beyond the individual annotator and item variance, we fit two more models containing the demographic or cultural zone variables:

$$H_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_E^\top \mathbf{E}_i + \beta_A^\top \mathbf{A}_i + \beta_G^\top \mathbf{G}_i + u_i + v_j + \epsilon_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{E}_i, \mathbf{A}_i, \mathbf{G}_i$ are ethnicity (when available), age, and gender one-hot vectors and $\beta_E, \beta_A, \beta_G$ are the corresponding coefficient vectors.

$$H_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_C^\top \mathbf{C}_i + u_i + v_j + \epsilon_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{C}_i is a one-hot vector of raters' cultural zones. We compared whether the models in Eqs. 2 and 3 have an improved fit compared to the base model in Eq. 1 via likelihood ratio tests (LRT; Wilks, 1938), which test whether the

¹For Likert, we also replicated the results with cumulative link mixed models; however, they did not allow for the same complexity in the random effect structure due to convergence errors.

²A low number of levels (as a rule of thumb, fewer than 6) can lead to imprecise estimates of random effects and convergence errors (Bolker et al., 2025). This was the case for the category (5 levels) and model name (4 levels) in CulturalFrames; conversation type (3 levels) and LM familiarity (3 levels) in PRISM; and degree of harm (4 levels) in DICES-990. These variables were included as fixed effects instead.

more complex model fits the data significantly better than the simpler one. We report the p -values from the LRT, with $p < 0.05$ indicating significantly better fit. The Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) procedure (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995) is applied to correct for multiple testing within the same research question (e.g., 8 tests for Demographics vs. Base Model reported in Table 2). In addition, we report the change in Akaike information criterion (ΔAIC ; Akaike, 1974), which balances goodness of fit against model complexity. To gauge how much of the rater-level variance is explained by culture or demographics, we also report the proportion reduction in rater variance ($\% \Delta \sigma_{\text{rater}}^2$), a pseudo- R^2 measure (Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002); see also Rights & Sterba (2020). See fixed effect estimates in Appendix C.3.

Results. Table 2 displays the aforementioned metrics. Strong evidence for the importance of demographics was found in all but two datasets (CulturalFrames and NLPositionality), with improvement in model fit (negative ΔAIC) ranging from -6.85 to -45.11 and a 5.25% average reduction in rater variance. Similarly, cultural zones significantly improved fit in all but two datasets (NLPositionality and CREHate), with ΔAIC ranging from -6.23 to -195.93 and an average 5.08% reduction in rater variance.

The exceptions can be largely explained by data limitations, e.g., cultural imbalance in NLPositionality. Missing rater ethnicity may explain the low variance reduction in D3 (-0.80) and the lack of significance for demographics in CulturalFrames. Overall, both demographics and culture have predictive power for safety annotations beyond rater and item random effects.

4.3. Culture improves prediction of safety ratings over demographics alone

To answer whether geo-cultural background impacts safety annotation beyond demographics, we fit two additional models building on Eq. 2: first, we add the cultural zone vector as another fixed effect, resulting in a D+CZ model that we compare to the demographics-only model. Second, we include interactions between cultural zone and demographic variables to test whether culture moderates how demographics affect safety ratings, resulting in a D×CZ model:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{ij} = & \beta_0 + \underbrace{\beta_C^\top \mathbf{C}_i + \beta_E^\top \mathbf{E}_i + \beta_A^\top \mathbf{A}_i + \beta_G^\top \mathbf{G}_i}_{\text{Culture and Demographic effects}} \\ & + \underbrace{\beta_{CE}^\top (\mathbf{C}_i \times \mathbf{E}_i) + \beta_{CA}^\top (\mathbf{C}_i \times \mathbf{A}_i) + \beta_{CG}^\top (\mathbf{C}_i \times \mathbf{G}_i)}_{\text{Culture and Demographic interactions}} \\ & + u_i + v_j + \epsilon_{ij} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Results. We report the same metrics as above in Table 3. In six out of eight datasets (all except DIVE and NLPosi-

Dataset	Demographics vs. Base Model			Cultural Zones vs. Base Model		
	p-value	ΔAIC	% $\Delta\sigma_{\text{rater}}^2$	p-value	ΔAIC	% $\Delta\sigma_{\text{rater}}^2$
DIVE	< 0.001*	-45.11	-8.90	0.003*	-7.52	-2.56
CulturalFrames	0.134	0.96	-4.43	< 0.001*	-41.62	-18.43
PRISM	< 0.001*	-16.71	-2.73	0.003*	-7.26	-1.42
DICES-990	< 0.001*	-11.13	-7.41	0.004*	-6.23	-7.61
NLPos	0.069	5.50	-10.52	0.344	4.37	-1.72
D3	< 0.001*	-25.96	-0.80	< 0.001*	-195.93	-5.22
CREHate	< 0.001*	-15.63	-5.58	0.203	0.38	-0.40
Severity	0.001*	-6.85	-1.59	< 0.001*	-41.68	-3.26

Table 2. Effect of demographics and culture on safety annotation prediction, compared to a base model accounting for variation in the raters and items. Negative ΔAIC indicates that the model with added demographics or cultural zones has a better fit than the base model. *: significant after the Benjamini-Hochberg correction for multiple testing.

tionality), we found significant evidence that geo-cultural background predicts safety ratings even after accounting for demographics (D+CZ vs. D; $p < 0.05$, ΔAIC ranging from -3.97 to -179.88 , average 4.64% reduction in rater variance).

We next test whether cultural background moderates how demographics affect safety ratings (e.g., millennial women in the Latin American cultural zone might rate things differently from millennial women in the Confucian zone). We compare models with and without the interaction term between the demographic and cultural zone variables. A significant LRT result indicates that the interaction terms (e.g., age effects differing across zones) improve prediction. Except for D3 ($\Delta\text{AIC} = -94.91$, $p < 0.001$), we did not find evidence that cultural background changes how demographics affect ratings: adding interaction terms (D×CZ) did not improve the fit of the model. However, D3 is the only dataset that recruited raters with balanced demographics (gender and age) within each cultural zone and has the largest number of annotations, which may be why the effect was detectable only there. Future work could explore whether this moderation effect holds in other datasets with balanced within-zone demographics.

5. Quantifying Geo-Cultural Blind Spots

The previous section showed that differences in raters’ cultural zones predict differences in safety perception. Here, we empirically quantify the blind spots resulting from the lack of geo-cultural pluralism: how many items would be misclassified as “safe” if certain cultural value perspectives were disregarded?

Cultural quadrants. In the previous section, we used cultural zones to operationalize cultural value diversity. Here, we take a coarser view, focusing on the quadrants formed by the Traditional-Secular and Survival-Self-Expression value axes of the Inglehart-Welzel cultural map, similarly to prior work (Zhang et al., 2025). As shown in Figure 1, Quadrant I

corresponds to higher Self-Expression and Secular values; II to higher Survival and Secular values; III to higher Survival and Traditional values; IV to higher Self-Expression and Traditional values. E.g., a country is assigned to Quadrant I if its Self-Expression and Secular value scores are both greater than zero. This coarser grouping ensures sufficient raters per group per item for the statistical analyses below.

Culturally sensitive items. We define an item to be culturally sensitive if, given annotations from multiple cultural quadrants, it would be deemed unsafe by exactly one quadrant. Consequently, excluding ratings from that quadrant would yield a false negative: an item marked as “safe” despite posing a risk to a specific cultural group. Algorithm 1 in Appendix D.1 details the procedure to identify such items, which we describe below.

For each item i and quadrant $q \in \{\text{I, II, III, IV}\}$, we collect the total count of ratings (n_{iq}) and the count of ratings labeled as unsafe (k_{iq}). For Likert-style ratings, we set the threshold τ_{label} to 1, treating any rating above 0 (“completely safe”) as unsafe, to minimize false negatives.³ To isolate cultural differences from demographic confounding (e.g., a quadrant composed entirely of Gen Z men might rate differently for demographic rather than cultural reasons), we apply a validity filter. A quadrant is considered valid only if it contains at least 3 votes ($n_{iq} \geq 3$, a common floor in practice (e.g., Calderon et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2024)). In addition, no single gender, ethnicity, or age group may account for 100% of the quadrant’s raters.⁴ Next, we use a uniform Beta(1, 1) prior to construct a posterior distribution Beta($1 + k_{iq}$, $1 + n_{iq} - k_{iq}$) for the underlying quadrant-level unsafe rate θ_{iq} . We then estimate the probability that the underlying quadrant-level unsafe rate exceeds 0.5 as

³For Severity, all items are considered unsafe unless τ_{label} is set to 3, requiring us to set it as the threshold.

⁴For D3, no ethnicity was reported; all raters from Quadrant II of CREHate, II of NLPositionality, and III of DICES-990 were of a single ethnicity. Hence, we avoided ethnicity thresholding for these datasets to preserve as many items as possible.

Dataset	D+CZ vs. D			D × CZ vs. D+CZ		
	p-value	ΔAIC	% $\Delta\sigma_{\text{rater}}^2$	p-value	ΔAIC	% $\Delta\sigma_{\text{rater}}^2$
DIVE	0.581	8.35	0.27	0.045	11.86	-2.13
CulturalFrames	< 0.001*	-41.19	-18.51	0.129	13.60	-10.44
PRISM	0.012*	-3.97	-1.11	0.064	30.59	-1.51
DICES-990	0.005*	-5.86	-6.53	0.059	-1.45	-4.68
NLPos	0.271	3.62	-2.11	0.141	3.06	-2.68
D3	< 0.001*	-179.88	-4.82	< 0.001*	-94.91	-3.00
CREHate	0.008*	-5.12	-1.12	0.727	11.87	-1.13
Severity	< 0.001*	-40.95	-3.20	0.111	24.53	-0.70

Table 3. *D+CZ vs. D*: Tests if adding cultural zones as a fixed effect improves fit over demographics alone. *D × CZ vs. D+CZ*: Tests if the interaction between cultural zones and demographics provides additional explanatory power. Negative ΔAIC indicates D+CZ (or D×CZ) model provides a better fit compared to D (or D+CZ). * significant after the Benjamini-Hochberg correction for multiple testing.

$H_{iq} = P(\theta_{iq} > 0.5)$, i.e., the probability that a majority of quadrant q would consider item i unsafe. Unlike point estimates from raw vote proportions, this Bayesian formulation regularizes estimates and quantifies uncertainty, which is particularly important for small sample sizes (e.g., $n_{iq} = 3$) (Gelman et al., 2013).

Finally, we compute $S_{iq} = H_{iq} \cdot \prod_{q' \neq q, q' \text{ is valid}} (1 - H_{iq'})$, the joint posterior probability (assuming independence across quadrants) that quadrant q would rate i as unsafe while all other valid quadrants would rate it as safe. Invalid quadrants are excluded from the calculation, and if there is only one valid quadrant for an item, we set $S_{iq} = 0$. An item is classified as culturally sensitive if $S_{iq} > 0.5$ for exactly one quadrant q .

Table 4 shows qualitative examples of items surfaced by our definition. Row 1 captures the Traditional vs. Secular divide on reverence for religious institutions. Row 2 illustrates the Self-Expression vs. Survival divide on stigmatization of sexuality. However, not all divides are clearly explainable; further qualitative research is needed. See five examples from each dataset in Appendix D.2.

Item	Ratings	Dataset
“Disgusting! How many more decades will it take for the Roman Catholic Church to wise up”	QI: 0/8 QIV: 5/5	D3
“Best wishes Uganda. Fighting back against violent homosexuality & the grooming”	QI: 11/15 QII: 1/5	CREHATE

Table 4. Qualitative examples of culturally sensitive items surfaced by our definition. QI: Secular/Self-Expression; QII: Secular/Survival; QIV: Traditional/Self-Expression. Fractions are (harmful ratings) / (total).

Results. Table 5 shows the results of applying the proposed algorithm on datasets with multiple valid cultural quadrant safety ratings per item (CulturalFrames is excluded because its nested design does not allow for cross-quadrant

comparison on the same items). Under a “more likely than not” threshold ($S_{iq} > 0.5$, assuming a high cost of false negatives), the rate of culturally sensitive items was roughly 10% across most datasets, despite differences in domain and task. The Severity dataset had a lower rate (3.0%). NLPositionality also showed an 11.1% rate, but this estimate should be interpreted with caution as the dataset contained only 9 items with valid multi-quadrant coverage. Under stricter thresholds (e.g., $S_{iq} > 0.7$), the overall rate drops to $\approx 3\%$; see Appendix D.3 for full sensitivity analysis. This suggests that failing to diversify the rater pool across cultural quadrants could lead to misclassifying a considerable proportion of unsafe content in a typical safety dataset.

6. LLMs for Pluralistic Safety Annotation

Given the non-trivial quantity of culturally sensitive items and high costs of culturally pluralistic annotation, a natural question is whether LLMs can help with or replicate human annotation (i.e., LLM-as-a-Judge (Inan et al., 2023)). First, we examine whether LLMs can emulate cultural quadrant judgments and thus serve as annotator surrogates. Second, we study whether LLMs can be used to identify culturally sensitive items to prioritize for human annotation, leading to more efficient allocation of annotation effort.

6.1. LLMs struggle to emulate cultural quadrant ratings

Experimental setting. To test whether LLMs can substitute for human annotators across cultural value quadrants, we perform the following experiment. Four LLMs were tasked with predicting the overall safety rating of each cultural quadrant q for each item i (i.e., whether $H_{iq} > 0.5$ for each quadrant, as obtained from Section 5) in a multi-label classification setting. We used DICES-990, CREHate, and D3, each associated with up to 4 binary quadrant-level safety ratings. CulturalFrames, NLPos, and Severity were excluded due to the low number of items annotated by multiple quadrants, and DIVE due to multimodality. A total of 7,119 items were split into training, validation, and test sets

Dataset	Culturally Sensitive Items						Dataset Statistics		
	I	II	III	IV	Total	Rate	Valid Items	Total Items	Quadrants
DIVE	27	9	85	2	123	13.9%	887	1000	I, II, III, IV
DICES-990	23	–	107	–	130	13.1%	990	990	I, III
D3	126	12	289	58	485	10.9%	4453	4554	I, II, III, IV
CREHate	33	92	–	49	174	11.1%	1562	1580	I, II, IV
NLPos	0	0	1	0	1	11.1%	9	299	I, II, III, IV
Severity	0	–	2	0	2	3.0%	66	66	I, III, IV

Table 5. Overview of culturally sensitive items across datasets. Quadrant columns I (Secular, Self-Expression), II (Secular, Survival), III (Traditional, Survival), IV (Traditional, Self-Expression) show the number of items labeled unsafe only by that quadrant ($S_{iq} > 0.5$). **Valid Items** denotes the subset of items with valid votes from at least two different quadrants. **Rate** is the percentage of Valid Items flagged as culturally sensitive.

($\approx 65/15/20\%$). See Appendix E.1 for details.

We fine-tuned two open-weight models representative of their respective model classes: DeBERTa-Large (He et al., 2021), a discriminative encoder model commonly used for text classification, and Gemma-3-4B (Team, 2025), a larger decoder-only model (see hyperparameters in Appendix F.1). We used masked binary cross-entropy loss, averaging only over known quadrant ratings (e.g., if the Quadrant III rating was missing or invalid, its cross-entropy with the prediction did not contribute to the overall loss). Each model was fine-tuned with 10 random seeds for 5 epochs each, selecting the best checkpoint based on average validation F1 across datasets. Hyperparameters are reported in Appendix F.1. Additionally, we prompted two small reasoning models, Gemini-3 Flash and GPT-5 Nano, to emulate raters from the four cultural quadrants (see Appendix F.3). To contextualize performance, we report the baseline of always predicting “unsafe”, which achieves $F1 = \frac{2 \cdot \text{prevalence}}{\text{prevalence} + 1}$.

Results. Figure 2 shows the average F1 across available cultural quadrants per dataset. While the models outperform the “Always Unsafe” baseline on DICES-990 and CREHate, they fail to consistently do so on D3, which contains judgments from all four quadrants. Specifically, all models performed worse or similarly to the baseline on Q II and Q IV (see detailed breakdown in Figure 10 in Appendix). Further, scaling model size and switching from an encoder (DeBERTa-Large, 435M) to a decoder-only model (Gemma-3, 4B) did not yield conclusive improvements. Overall, predicting the judgment of a cultural quadrant is difficult, and current LM-based classifiers do not reliably learn this decision boundary from available data. This cautions against the use of prompted or fine-tuned language models to replace human safety judgments, motivating the need for culturally pluralistic human safety annotation.

6.2. LLMs can help triage culturally sensitive items

Experimental setting. Given the drawbacks of using LLMs to emulate judgments of raters across diverse quad-

Figure 2. Average F1 per dataset on predicting safety judgments of cultural value quadrants. 95% CIs obtained via hierarchical bootstrap ($B = 10,000$) at random seed and item level.

rants, we investigate whether these models can still be used to identify culturally sensitive items ($S_{iq} > 0.5$, as defined in Section 5), so that they can be prioritized for human annotation. We fine-tune two language models (DeBERTa-Large and Gemma-3-4B) on two binary classification tasks: unanimously safe vs. unanimously unsafe (safe-unsafe) and unanimously safe vs. culturally sensitive (safe-sensitive). The safe-unsafe task serves as a reference, allowing us to compare classifier performance on identifying culturally sensitive items vs. identifying uncontroversially unsafe ones. Here, we focus on the D3 dataset containing the largest number of culturally sensitive items (see Appendix E.2 for cross-dataset experiments). We select all 485 such items and randomly sample 485 unanimously safe (all quadrants voted as safe) and 485 unanimously unsafe (all quadrants voted unsafe) items. For each task, the 970 items are randomly split into training/validation/test sets ($\approx 65/15/20\%$), with no item overlap between splits (see Appendix E.2).

Results. Figure 3 highlights that for both models, there is a statistically significant decrease in F1 score ($\approx 16\%$ for DeBERTa; $\approx 14\%$ for Gemma) from the safe-vs-unsafe to the safe-vs-sensitive task. This indicates that detecting sensitive content is a more nuanced task than detecting unsafe content. Even so, Gemma significantly outperforms the baseline (0.72 F1, $p = 0.044$), and DeBERTa shows a

similar trend (0.71 F1, $p = 0.071$). Importantly, training transfers from the safe-sensitive task to the safe-unsafe task, but not the other way around (Appendix E.2). This suggests that training on culturally sensitive examples yields richer representations of unsafety. Overall, fine-tuned LMs can help prioritize items for culturally pluralistic annotation.

Figure 3. Performance degradation from safe-vs-unsafe to safe-vs-sensitive tasks. **: p -value < 0.001.

7. Conclusion and Practical Takeaways

Our comparative analysis of safety datasets reveals gaps in geo-cultural variable reporting and diversification, as well as a lack of robust methodology to assess the impact of rater attributes (such as cultural values and demographics) on safety annotation. We propose a methodological framework operationalizing geo-cultural values via the Inglehart-Welzel cultural map (Inglehart & Welzel, 2005) and multilevel modeling. Applying this approach to a broad range of datasets, we provide quantitative evidence of the importance of geo-cultural values in safety annotation, recommending that AI safety practitioners diversify the rater pool with respect to both demographic and geo-cultural factors. Specifically, lack of geo-cultural representation could lead to $\approx 10\%$ of unsafe items being missed in current datasets, harming deployment in underrepresented cultural value quadrants. Fine-tuned and prompted LMs should not be used to replace human judgment from diverse cultural quadrants, but fine-tuned LMs can help prioritize culturally sensitive items for human annotation.

Practical takeaways. Based on our review of the available datasets, we recommend the following data collection strategies to ensure cultural coverage: 1) stratify raters not only on age, gender, and ethnicity, but also on cultural quadrant (for example, using the Inglehart-Welzel map); 2) in the absence of cultural self-identification or value survey data, use country of longest residence or country of birth (or more fine-grained regional attributes) as a proxy for cultural background; 3) avoid brittle methods to analyze rater dis-

agreements; use multilevel models to control for variation in raters and items; 4) use a fine-tuned LLM classifier to prioritize culturally sensitive items for human annotation if necessitated by budget constraints.

8. Limitations and Future Work

The main limitation of our study is the reductionist nature of the division into cultural zones or quadrants. The two dimensions of the IW cultural map “are only indicators of much broader underlying dimensions of cross-cultural variation” (Inglehart & Welzel, 2005) and may not capture the full complexity of geo-cultural variation. The IW map may also reflect cultural essentialism and stigmatization of developing countries (Dervin et al., 2020). The World Values Survey, while widely adopted as one of the most comprehensive global surveys, does not survey all countries and does not have up-to-date data for each of them. In addition, the variation is only captured at the country level, while nuanced safety issues can be surfaced on localized, regional levels (Rastogi et al., 2026). Reliance on surveys and country-as-a-culture proxies risks oversimplifying culture (Alkhamissi et al., 2025), but is a necessary pragmatic starting point to incorporate cultural diversity in safety data.

The cultural sensitivity analysis in Sec. 5 is sensitive to available quadrants. Since not all datasets recruited participants along the four quadrants or ensured demographic diversity within each, the percentage of culturally sensitive items could be over- or underestimated. Further, the validity filtering reduces but does not eliminate demographic confounding, since perfectly balanced demographics within each quadrant are not achievable with current data. Finally, quadrant-level analysis may group countries that share value axes signs but differ substantially (e.g., the Confucian and Orthodox Europe cultural zones), resulting in high within-quadrant disagreement. Accordingly, these results should be interpreted as a rough empirical estimate based on the data available. We hope that future work will collect a dataset that is diverse both culturally and demographically, building on the practical takeaways from our study.

In Sec. 6.2, experiments with vision-language models were not conducted, limiting the generalization of findings to the visual modality. Since text+image classification is generally more difficult than text-only classification, we expect our findings on cultural quadrant emulation to hold in the multimodal setting. In addition, in-distribution fine-tuning requires annotated data, constraining the practical use of fine-tuned triage models for new datasets.

While our analyses were conducted on peer-reviewed datasets, data reliability may be affected by socio-economic factors (Sambasivan et al., 2021), necessitating careful approaches to global rater recruitment in future work.

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Impact statement

Current data collection policies primarily focus on age, gender, ethnicity pluralism, overlooking geo-cultural factors. We hope that our work will spread awareness of the importance of geo-cultural factors in safety annotations, consequently encouraging geo-culturally diverse rater recruitment. Our analyses and practical takeaways clarify how to operationalize cultural value diversity to recruit representative raters, which attributes to collect, and how to allocate the raters more effectively by identifying culturally sensitive items. Overall, we hope our work will result in AI models that are safe globally and are more robust to culturally sensitive safety ratings.

We would also like to acknowledge some potential foreseeable negative impacts of our work. First, while geo-cultural variation is important, over-indexing on solely this aspect of human value differences poses a risk of neglecting other sources of variation in values, such as individual moral values. Second, over-reliance on the World Values Survey may result in some countries that were not present in the survey or that obtained inaccurate value estimates to be misrepresented. Third, as more data is collected about raters, there are increased privacy concerns as the potential for de-anonymization increases. Fourth, data collected to measure geo-cultural differences could be used for stereotyping or generalizations about individuals based on their background (ecological fallacy (Ess et al., 2001)). Fifth, practitioners may interpret disagreements always in favor of the cultural group that labels items as unsafe instead of targeted modifications to the model depending on deployment locale, which may result in over-refusals (Cui et al., 2025) or censorship effects (Amironesei & Díaz, 2023; Mirowski et al., 2024).

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A. Inglehart-Welzel Cultural Map

Figure 4 shows the 2023 version of the Inglehart-Welzel cultural map (Inglehart & Welzel, 2005). Countries can be grouped into cultural zones based on values (not necessarily based on geography, e.g. see Philippines in the Latin America zone).

Figure 4. Inglehart-Welzel Cultural Map of the world displaying cultural zones and countries within them.

B. Preprocessing Details

DIVE

PREPROCESSING

- Exclude raters with the “filtered out” flag.
- Exclude items that were attention checks.
- Exclude a single outlier rater that had country of residence Mexico.

LINEAR MODELING ASSUMPTIONS

- Use “harmful_to_you” as harmfulness score, since our study’s focus is on subjective safety perception.
- Exclude “unsure” ratings.
- Use CoB for cultural zone and drop raters with NA for CoB.
- As a result, excluded raters with CoB values of ‘Barbados’, ‘Cuba’, ‘DATA_EXPIRED’, ‘Dominican Republic’, ‘Kuwait’, ‘Nepal’, ‘Panama’, ‘Sri Lanka’, ‘Sudan’, ‘Syrian Arab Republic’, ‘United Arab Emirates’.

CulturalFrames

PREPROCESSING

- Exclude raters with sex “CONSENT_REVOKED” and “Prefer not to say”.
- Age is mapped to generational labels (GenZ, Millennial, GenX, Boomer) according to Beresford Research (2026).
- Use country of birth for cultural zone assignment (since CoB = CoN = CoLR, and all are superior to CoR).

LINEAR MODELING ASSUMPTIONS

- Use “is_stereotypical” as harmfulness score.

PRISM

PREPROCESSING

- Exclude raters with “Prefer not to say” or “Other” for ethnicity, gender, age group.

LINEAR MODELING ASSUMPTIONS

- Use 100 - “safety score” as harmfulness score.
- Use CoB for cultural zone and drop raters with NA for CoB.
- As a result, excluded raters with CoB values of ‘Afghanistan’, ‘Cuba’, “Côte d’Ivoire”, ‘Guyana’, ‘Honduras’, ‘Jamaica’, ‘Malawi’, ‘Prefer not to say’, ‘Sri Lanka’, ‘Sudan’, ‘Tonga’.

DICES-990

PREPROCESSING

- The subset of the data with expert annotation of topic of harm was used.
- Use fine-grained self-reported ethnicity categories, after that, exclude raters with NA, “Other” and “Prefer not to answer” as response to ethnicity.
- Assign self-described gender (non M, F) into “nonbinary” category.

LINEAR MODELING ASSUMPTIONS

- Use a subset of the data with expert annotations of degrees of harm (306 items).
- Use “Q_overall” as harmfulness score, exclude “Unsure” ratings.

NLPositionality

PREPROCESSING

- Exclude raters with NA or “No response” as response to ethnicity.
- Exclude raters with “No response” or NA as response to gender, assign self-described gender (non M, F) into “nonbinary” category.
- Age is mapped to generational labels (GenZ, Millennial, GenX, Boomer) according to [Beresford Research \(2026\)](#).
- Raters with age below GenZ (11) or NA for age are excluded.

LINEAR MODELING ASSUMPTIONS

- Use “litw” as harmfulness score (1 harmful, -1 not harmful), exclude Unsure (0) instances.
- Use CoLR for cultural zone and drop raters with NA for CoLR.
- As a result, excluded raters with CoB values of ‘Dominican Republic’, ‘Nepal’.

D3

PREPROCESSING

- No filtering was needed.

LINEAR MODELING ASSUMPTIONS

- Use “rating_raw” as harmfulness score (1 harmful, -1 not harmful), exclude Did Not Understand (-1) instances.
- Use CoR for cultural zone and drop raters with NA for CoR.
- As a result, excluded raters with CoB values of ‘United Arab Emirates’.

CREHate

PREPROCESSING

- Exclude raters with NA for age.
- Exclude raters with fine-grained “Other” ethnicities that have ≤ 2 raters, but keep “Mixed” ethnicity as a larger category to be consistent with DICES-990.
- Age is mapped to generational labels (GenZ, Millennial, GenX, Boomer) according to [Beresford Research \(2026\)](#).

LINEAR MODELING ASSUMPTIONS

- Use “annotation” as harmfulness score (1 harmful, 0 not harmful), exclude Unsure (2) instances.

Severity

PREPROCESSING

- Exclude raters with NA or “Prefer not to disclose” for gender.
- Exclude raters with NA for age.
- Exclude raters with ethnicity containing “Other” or that have a unique ethnicity.
- Assign self-described gender (non M, F) into “nonbinary” category.
- Convert “likert” scores to numerical values in the following way:
 - “Not at all upsetting”: 0
 - “A little upsetting”: 1
 - “Somewhat upsetting”: 2
 - “Very upsetting”: 3
 - “Extremely upsetting”: 4

LINEAR MODELING ASSUMPTIONS

- Use converted “likert” scores as harmfulness scores.
- Exclude items with NA for likert score.

B.1. Comparison of demographic and geo-cultural attribute coverage

Table 6 shows the coverage of demographic and geo-cultural rater attributes across datasets.

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	DICES-990	PRISM	D3	NLPos	DIVE	Severity	CREHate	CultFrames
Total annotations	51,340	7,517	153,251	6,348	31,930	48,964	41,714	9,922
Unique raters	119	1,303	4,309	505	636	1,416	1,039	379
Gender								
Man	57 (47.9%)	652 (50.0%)	2,149 (49.9%)	185 (36.6%)	323 (50.8%)	733 (51.8%)	515 (49.6%)	189 (49.9%)
Woman	60 (50.4%)	633 (48.6%)	2,119 (49.2%)	260 (51.5%)	313 (49.2%)	673 (47.5%)	508 (48.9%)	190 (50.1%)
Non-binary/Other	2 (1.7%)	18 (1.4%)	41 (1.0%)	60 (11.9%)	–	10 (0.7%)	16 (1.5%)	–
Ethnicity								
White	27 (22.7%)	892 (68.5%)	–	312 (61.8%)	128 (20.1%)	519 (36.7%)	673 (64.8%)	–
Asian	53 (44.5%)	91 (7.0%)	–	94 (18.6%)	254 (39.9%)	803 (56.7%)	183 (17.6%)	–
Black/African	15 (12.6%)	117 (9.0%)	–	38 (7.5%)	123 (19.3%)	57 (4.0%)	157 (15.1%)	–
Latino/Hispanic	16 (13.4%)	117 (9.0%)	–	51 (10.1%)	131 (20.6%)	–	–	–
Middle Eastern	–	12 (0.9%)	–	2 (0.4%)	–	–	7 (0.7%)	–
Indigenous/Pacific Isl.	7 (5.9%)	8 (0.6%)	–	6 (1.2%)	–	30 (2.1%)	–	–
Mixed/Other	1 (0.8%)	66 (5.1%)	–	2 (0.4%)	–	–	19 (1.8%)	–
Age Group								
Gen Z / 18–30	18 (15.1%)	253 (19.4%)	2,019 (46.9%)	374 (74.1%)	212 (33.3%)	150 (10.6%)	302 (29.1%)	147 (38.8%)
Millennial / 25–44	67 (56.3%)	604 (46.4%)	1,495 (34.7%)	85 (16.8%)	215 (33.8%)	445 (31.4%)	466 (44.9%)	163 (43.0%)
Gen X / 35–54	34 (28.6%)	355 (27.2%)	–	34 (6.7%)	209 (32.9%)	662 (46.8%)	200 (19.2%)	61 (16.1%)
Boomer / 55+	–	91 (7.0%)	795 (18.4%)	12 (2.4%)	–	159 (11.2%)	71 (6.8%)	8 (2.1%)
Geographic Attributes								
Country of Birth	–	69 countries	–	–	50 countries	–	–	10 countries
Country of Residence	2 countries	34 countries	21 countries	11 countries	2 countries	8 countries	–	22 countries
Country of Longest Res.	–	–	–	16 countries	–	–	–	–
Country of Nationality	–	–	–	–	40 countries	–	5 countries	10 countries

Table 6. Demographic and geo-cultural attribute distributions across datasets. Counts (%).

C. Multilevel Modeling

C.1. Comparison of Country of Birth, Residence, and Nationality as a Basis for Cultural Cluster Assignment

In Table 7, we compare models fitted on the PRISM dataset (since it is the only dataset containing both diverse countries of residence and birth), but ablating on how we assign a cultural zone to each annotator (see cultural zone model specification for PRISM in Table 116). Instead of using country of birth, we also use country of residence and their combination (e.g., English-Speaking country of residence with Catholic Europe country of birth). Cultural zones assigned using CoB were the most parsimonious explanation of safety ratings, as indicated by the lower AIC value for that model compared to all other configurations, including the base model.

Model	npar	AIC(↓)	logLik	χ^2	p
Null	9	59505.8	-29743.9	—	—
Culture (CoB)	16	59498.5	-29733.3	21.26	0.003
Culture (CoR)	15	59501.6	-29735.8	16.12	0.013
Culture (CoB×CoR)	31	59517.4	-29727.7	32.40	0.071

Table 7. Comparison of cultural zone predictiveness when based on country of birth (CoB), country of residence (CoR), and their combination (CoB × CoR) in PRISM.

Similar results were observed in the DIVE dataset (Table 8), comparing nationality and country of birth as a proxy (see cultural zone model specification for DIVE in Table 77).

Model	npar	AIC(↓)	logLik	χ^2	p
Null	5	84658.1	-42324.1	—	—
Culture (CoB)	12	84650.6	-42313.30	21.52	0.003
Culture (CoN)	13	84665.1	-42319.6	8.98	0.344

Table 8. Comparison of cultural zone predictiveness when based on country of birth (CoB) and country of residence (CoN) in DIVE.

On the NLPositionality dataset, we were able to compare CoR and CoLR, similarly confirming the intuition that CoLR is a better predictor.

Model	npar	AIC(↓)	logLik	χ^2	p
Null	3	5273.4	-2633.7	—	—
Culture (CoLR)	8	5277.7	-2630.9	5.6	0.3435
Culture (CoR)	7	5278.5	-2632.3	2.86	0.581

Table 9. Comparison of cultural zone predictiveness when based on country of residence (CoR) and country of longest residence (CoLR) in NLPositionality.

C.2. Cultural Values vs. Cultural Zones vs. Cultural Quadrants as the Predictor Variable

We also perform analysis by using the continuous cultural value axes scores from the WVS instead of the coarser cultural zones. As can be seen in Table 10, cultural zones provide lower Δ AIC values in the majority of the datasets compared to all possible configurations (Traditional-Secular score alone (Trad), Survival-Self-Expression score alone (SurvS), adding them separately (T+S), and adding their interaction (T×S)). We also find that value quadrants are similarly predictive as reported in Tables 12, 13, confirming the validity of quadrant-level analysis in Sections 5, 6. In Table 11 we also report demographics variable experiments with the best cultural value configuration instead of the cultural zone as the predictive variable for completeness.

C.3. Fixed Effect Estimates

Figures 5, 6, 7, 8 display forest plots with fixed effect estimates from core multilevel models (Demographics, Cultural Zone, D+CZ) across datasets. Full model specifications and estimates available in Appendix G.

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Dataset	Cult Zones			Values (Trad)			Values (SurvS)			Values (T+S)			Values (T×S)		
	p	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2$	p	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2$	p	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2$	p	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2$	p	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2$
DIVE	0.003*	-7.52	-2.56	< 0.001*	-9.75	-1.91	< 0.001*	-10.18	-1.98	0.001*	-9.75	-2.08	< 0.001*	-13.98	-2.99
CulturalFrames	< 0.001*	<u>-41.62</u>	-18.43	0.160	0.03	0.10	0.030*	-2.71	-2.97	< 0.001*	-20.38	-8.75	< 0.001*	<u>-29.88</u>	-13.63
PRISM	0.003*	<u>-7.26</u>	-1.42	0.654	1.80	0.08	0.738	1.89	0.09	0.903	3.80	0.18	0.698	4.57	0.13
DICES-990	0.004*	<u>-6.23</u>	-7.61	0.004*	-6.23	-7.61	0.004*	-6.23	-7.61	0.004*	-6.23	-7.61	0.004*	-6.23	-7.61
NLPos	0.344	4.37	-1.72	0.041*	<u>-2.19</u>	-1.30	0.689	1.84	-0.08	0.056	-1.78	-1.82	0.115	0.06	-1.92
D3	< 0.001*	-195.93	-5.22	< 0.001*	-86.91	-2.31	< 0.001*	-104.25	-2.77	< 0.001*	-107.02	-2.87	< 0.001*	-119.96	-3.23
CREHate	0.203	0.38	-0.40	0.042*	-2.15	-0.51	0.743	1.89	0.03	0.001*	<u>-9.13</u>	-2.35	0.004*	-7.14	-2.35
Severity	< 0.001*	-41.68	-3.26	< 0.001*	-33.74	-2.54	< 0.001*	-23.60	-1.79	< 0.001*	<u>-37.40</u>	-2.87	< 0.001*	<u>-46.43</u>	-3.59

Table 10. Comparison of using cultural zones vs. cultural axes values directly as the predictive variable. Highest negative ΔAIC (best fit) for each dataset is underlined. * $p < 0.05$.

Dataset	Best CV Config	D+CV vs. D			D × CV vs. D+CV		
		p-value	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2_{rater}$	p-value	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2_{rater}$
DIVE	Trad×SurvS	0.369	1.19	0.03	0.248	4.93	-0.35
CulturalFrames	Trad×SurvS	< 0.001*	-29.23	-13.54	0.007*	-3.18	-9.09
PRISM	Trad	0.828	1.95	0.10	0.324	9.45	-0.15
DICES-990	Trad	0.005*	-5.86	-6.53	0.059	-1.45	-4.68
NLPos	Trad	0.025*	-3.06	-1.64	0.765	8.66	-1.16
D3	Trad×SurvS	< 0.001*	-112.07	-3.02	< 0.001*	-92.62	-2.76
CREHate	Trad+SurvS	0.022*	-3.62	-1.27	0.614	20.30	-2.79
Severity	Trad×SurvS	< 0.001*	-41.90	-3.26	0.280	33.40	-0.25

Table 11. D+CV vs. D: Tests if adding continuous cultural values as a fixed effect improves fit over demographics alone. D × CV vs. D+CV: Tests if the interaction between cultural values and demographics provides additional explanatory power. Best CV Config indicates the cultural value configuration with the lowest AIC compared to null.

Dataset	Cultural Zones			Value Quadrants		
	p-value	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2_{rater}$	p-value	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2_{rater}$
DIVE	0.003*	-7.52	-2.56	< 0.001*	<u>-10.69</u>	-2.42
CulturalFrames	< 0.001*	<u>-41.62</u>	-18.43	0.004*	<u>-7.05</u>	-1.92
PRISM	0.003*	<u>-7.26</u>	-1.42	0.734	4.72	0.17
DICES-990	0.004*	<u>-6.23</u>	-7.61	0.004*	-6.23	-7.61
NLPos	0.344	4.37	-1.72	0.186	<u>1.19</u>	-1.68
D3	< 0.001*	-195.93	-5.22	< 0.001*	<u>-208.59</u>	-5.52
CREHate	0.203	0.38	-0.40	0.002*	<u>-8.08</u>	-2.34
Severity	< 0.001*	<u>-41.68</u>	-3.26	< 0.001*	<u>-40.53</u>	-3.12

Table 12. Comparison of using cultural zones (categorical clusters) vs. cultural value quadrants (discretised from Trad/SurvS axes) as predictors. Highest negative ΔAIC (best fit) for each dataset is underlined. * $p < 0.05$.

Dataset	D+Q vs. D			D × Q vs. D+Q		
	p-value	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2_{rater}$	p-value	ΔAIC	$\% \Delta \sigma^2_{rater}$
DIVE	0.164	0.88	-0.37	0.161	13.02	-0.95
CulturalFrames	0.001*	-10.12	-3.27	0.207	6.70	-5.02
PRISM	0.942	5.61	0.26	0.365	25.09	-0.20
DICES-990	0.005*	-5.86	-6.53	0.059	-1.45	-4.68
NLPos	0.151	0.69	-2.02	0.186	4.72	-2.68
D3	< 0.001*	-194.06	-5.15	< 0.001*	-72.85	-2.25
CREHate	0.012*	-4.83	-1.36	0.975	22.38	-1.13
Severity	< 0.001*	-38.54	-2.97	0.511	23.85	0.11

Table 13. D+Q vs. D: Tests if adding cultural value quadrants as a fixed effect improves fit over demographics alone. D × Q vs. D+Q: Tests if the interaction between quadrants and demographics provides additional explanatory power. Quadrants are discretised from the Trad and SurvS cultural value axes. * $p < 0.05$.

Figure 5. Forest plots of fixed-effect coefficients (point estimates with 95% CI) for the Demographics, Cultural Zone, and Demographics + Cultural Zone models (1/4). Red points: $p < 0.05$; blue points: $p \geq 0.05$. Reference levels are shown in each panel subtitle.

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Figure 6. Forest plots of fixed-effect coefficients (point estimates with 95% CI) for the Demographics, Cultural Zone, and Demographics + Cultural Zone models (2/4). Red points: $p < 0.05$; blue points: $p \geq 0.05$. Reference levels are shown in each panel subtitle.

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Figure 7. Forest plots of fixed-effect coefficients (point estimates with 95% CI) for the Demographics, Cultural Zone, and Demographics + Cultural Zone models (3/4). Red points: $p < 0.05$; blue points: $p \geq 0.05$. Reference levels are shown in each panel subtitle.

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Figure 8. Forest plots of fixed-effect coefficients (point estimates with 95% CI) for the Demographics, Cultural Zone, and Demographics + Cultural Zone models (4/4). Red points: $p < 0.05$; blue points: $p \geq 0.05$. Reference levels are shown in each panel subtitle.

D. Culturally sensitive items

D.1. Algorithm

The full algorithm to identify culturally sensitive items is presented below in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Cultural Sensitivity Scoring

Input: Dataset \mathcal{D} , quadrants $Q = \{I, II, III, IV\}$; unsafe rating threshold τ_{vote} ; number of raters threshold $\tau_n = 3$; gender, age, ethnicity homogeneity thresholds $\tau_{g,a,e}$; priors $\alpha = 1, \beta = 1$.

Output: Cultural Sensitivity scores $S_{i,q}$ for every item i and quadrant q .

// Phase 1: Aggregation & Validity

```

for each item  $i \in \mathcal{D}$  do
  for each quadrant  $q \in Q$  do
     $n_{i,q} \leftarrow \text{Count}(\text{votes for } i \text{ in } q)$ 
     $k_{i,q} \leftarrow \text{Count}(\text{unsafe votes } (\leq \tau_{\text{vote}}) \text{ for } i \text{ in } q)$ 
    // Calculate max homogeneity per demographic axis
     $h_{i,q}^{\text{ethn}} \leftarrow \text{max}(\% \text{Ethnicity groups in } q)$ 
     $h_{i,q}^{\text{gend}} \leftarrow \text{max}(\% \text{Gender groups in } q)$ 
     $h_{i,q}^{\text{age}} \leftarrow \text{max}(\% \text{Age groups in } q)$ 
    // Valid if populated AND diverse across all axes
    if  $n_{i,q} \geq \tau_n$  and  $h_{i,q}^{\text{ethn}} < \tau_e$  and  $h_{i,q}^{\text{gend}} < \tau_g$  and  $h_{i,q}^{\text{age}} < \tau_a$  then
       $v_{i,q} \leftarrow 1$ 
    else
       $v_{i,q} \leftarrow 0$ 
    end if
  end for
end for

```

// Phase 2: Obtain the Probability

```

for each item  $i \in \mathcal{D}$  do
  for each quadrant  $q \in Q$  do
     $p'_{i,q} \leftarrow 1 - F_{\text{Beta}}(0.5; \alpha + k_{i,q}, \beta + n_{i,q} - k_{i,q})$ 
     $p_{i,q} \leftarrow p'_{i,q} \cdot v_{i,q}$  {Zero out if invalid}
  end for
end for

```

// Phase 3: Obtain the Sensitivity Score

```

for each item  $i \in \mathcal{D}$  do
  for each target  $q \in Q$  do
     $S_{i,q} \leftarrow p_{i,q}$ 
     $C_{\text{opp}} \leftarrow 0$ 
    for each opponent  $r \in Q \setminus \{q\}$  do
      // If opponent  $r$  is invalid,  $p_{i,r} = 0$ , so we multiply by 1.0
       $S_{i,q} \leftarrow S_{i,q} \cdot (1 - p_{i,r})$ 
       $C_{\text{opp}} \leftarrow C_{\text{opp}} + v_{i,r}$ 
    end for
    // Require at least one valid opponent
    if  $C_{\text{opp}} == 0$  then
       $S_{i,q} \leftarrow 0$ 
    end if
  end for
end for
return  $S$ 

```

D.2. Examples

Examples can be found at asaakyan.github.io/culture-safety. The alignment with cultural quadrant values is not always obvious, showing potential for future qualitative research on quadrant-level disagreements and motivating the need for more representative quadrant data collection.

D.3. Threshold Sensitivity Analysis

We conduct a threshold sensitivity analysis to see how the rate of culturally sensitive items would change if we adjust S_{iq} (the joint posterior probability that, among valid quadrants, only quadrant q rated the item as unsafe) and τ_{majority} (the threshold on θ_{iq} used in $H_{iq} = P(\theta_{iq} > \tau_{\text{majority}})$).

Fixing $\tau_{\text{majority}} = 0.5$ (the criterion used in the main text), Table 14 shows how the average Culturally Sensitive Item rate would differ as we increase the threshold for S_{iq} . Though our main results rely on the “more likely than not” standard, even when the threshold is increased to 0.7, most datasets display a non-trivial rate of culturally sensitive items (see the breakdown in Table 15). Heatmaps showing sensitivity to both thresholds can be found in Figure 9.

Table 14. CSI (%) aggregated across all six datasets as a function of the S_{iq} threshold ($\tau_{\text{majority}} = 0.5$).

S_{iq} threshold	CSI (%)	Mean \pm Std
0.5	10.53 \pm	3.87
0.6	8.02 \pm	3.72
0.7	3.43 \pm	2.74
0.8	1.39 \pm	1.46
0.9	0.41 \pm	0.49
0.95	0.09 \pm	0.13
0.99	0.00 \pm	0.00

Table 15. Culturally Sensitive Item rate (CSI, %) per dataset as a function of the cultural sensitivity threshold S_{iq} , with $\tau_{\text{majority}} = 0.5$ as the threshold for considering a quadrant’s judgment to be unsafe.

Dataset	S_{iq} threshold						
	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.99
DIVE	13.87	10.82	5.64	1.80	0.45	0.00	0.00
DICES-990	13.13	10.71	7.47	3.94	1.31	0.30	0.00
NLPos	11.11	11.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
D3	10.89	7.23	3.37	1.48	0.43	0.07	0.00
CREHate	11.14	6.72	2.56	1.09	0.26	0.19	0.00
Severity	3.03	1.52	1.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Mean</i>	10.53	8.02	3.43	1.39	0.41	0.09	0.00

Figure 9. Sensitivity of culturally sensitive item rate to two thresholds: S_{iq} (the joint posterior probability that, among valid quadrants, only quadrant q rated the item as unsafe) and τ_{majority} (the threshold on θ_{iq} used in $H_{iq} = P(\theta_{iq} > \tau_{\text{majority}})$).

E. Classifier Experiments

E.1. Quadrant-level prediction

As described in Section 5, each item can be associated with its estimated probability of each of the four quadrants rating it as harmful (H_{iq}). We assemble a dataset where each item is associated with a binarized quadrant-level safety rating (e.g., 1 if Quadrant I is more likely to rate it as unsafe i.e. $H_{iI} > 0.5$, 0 for Quadrant II if $H_{iII} < 0.5$, etc.). We combine the data from D3, CREHate, and DICES-990 and split it into training, validation, and testing sets. Crucially, no item is present in multiple sets. Table 16 shows the statistics for the train set, Table 17 for the validation set, and Table 18 for the test set. Figure 10 shows the detailed breakdown of model performance among quadrants by dataset.

Dataset	Label I			Label II			Label III			Label IV		
	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe
crehate	562	449	44.4	449	440	49.5	-	-	-	515	375	42.1
d3	1457	1360	48.3	509	298	36.9	1139	1694	59.8	794	835	51.3
dices	552	82	12.9	-	-	-	491	143	22.6	-	-	-

Table 16. Train set 0/1 label distribution on the test set across datasets and quadrants. - = no valid annotations for that quadrant in that dataset.

Dataset	Label I			Label II			Label III			Label IV		
	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe
crehate	138	114	45.2	112	110	49.5	-	-	-	128	93	42.1
d3	364	342	48.4	128	77	37.6	287	423	59.6	202	207	50.6
dices	138	20	12.7	-	-	-	123	35	22.2	-	-	-

Table 17. Validation set 0/1 label distribution on the test set across datasets and quadrants. - = no valid annotations for that quadrant in that dataset.

Dataset	Label I			Label II			Label III			Label IV		
	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe
crehate	175	140	44.4	139	137	49.6	-	-	-	162	116	41.7
d3	456	427	48.4	161	92	36.4	358	529	59.6	249	260	51.1
dices	173	25	12.6	-	-	-	153	45	22.7	-	-	-

Table 18. Test set 0/1 label distribution on the test set across datasets and quadrants. - = no valid annotations for that quadrant in that dataset.

E.2. Culturally sensitive item identification

Table 19 shows the label distribution across train, validation, test sets for the safe-vs-unsafe task; Table 20 for the safe-vs-sensitive task. Note the number of items is the same between tasks to enable a more fair comparison between them.

Cross-dataset and cross-task generalization. Figure 11 shows limited cross-dataset generalization: training on D3 does not generalize to CREHate and DICES-990, neither for safe-vs-unsafe nor for safe-vs-sensitive classification, with the exception of Gemma on the safe-vs-unsafe task in DICES-990. Training on all datasets together does not yield conclusive improvements. Figure 12 shows that models trained on the safe-vs-unsafe task do not generalize to the safe-vs-sensitive task. However, models trained on the safe-vs-sensitive task do achieve above-random performance on the safe-vs-unsafe task. This suggests that training to detect culturally sensitive items teaches a richer notion of unsafety than training on unanimously unsafe content alone.

Figure 10. Model performance by quadrant and dataset. 95% CIs obtained via hierarchical bootstrap on random seed and item level.

Table 19. 0/1 label distribution for the safety classification task (safe vs. unsafe) across datasets and splits. Label 1 = unanimously unsafe; label 0 = unanimously safe.

Dataset	Train			Val			Test		
	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe	0	1	% unsafe
crehate	111	111	50.0	28	28	50.0	35	35	50.0
d3	310	310	50.0	78	78	50.0	97	97	50.0
dices	57	57	50.0	15	15	50.0	18	18	50.0

Table 20. 0/1 label distribution for the sensitive item identification task (safe vs. culturally sensitive) across datasets and splits. Label 1 = culturally sensitive; label 0 = unanimously safe.

Dataset	Train			Val			Test		
	0	1	% sensitive	0	1	% sensitive	0	1	% sensitive
crehate	111	111	50.0	28	28	50.0	35	35	50.0
d3	310	310	50.0	78	78	50.0	97	97	50.0
dices	57	57	50.0	15	15	50.0	18	18	50.0

Figure 11. Cross-dataset generalization for safe-vs-unsafe and safe-vs-sensitive tasks. 95% CIs obtained with hierarchical bootstrap on the item and random seed level. p-values indicate whether difference from the “Always Unsafe” baseline is significant.

Figure 12. Cross-task generalization for safe-vs-unsafe and safe-vs-sensitive tasks on D3. 95% CIs obtained with hierarchical bootstrap on the item and random seed level. p-values indicate whether difference from the “Always Unsafe” baseline is significant.

F. Language Model Hyperparameters

F.1. Fine-tuning Hyperparameters

We used the following hyperparameters for fine-tuning the models:

- **DeBERTa-Large**
 - Model version `deberta-v3-large`
 - Fine-tuning type: full parameter
 - Batch size: 16
 - Learning rate: $2e-5$
 - Epochs: 5
 - weight decay 0.01
- **Gemma-3-4B**
 - Model version `gemma-3-4b-it`
 - Fine-tuning type: full parameter
 - Batch size: 8
 - Learning rate: $2e-5$
 - Epochs: 5
 - weight decay 0.01

All open model fine-tuning was ran on 4 A100 40GB NVIDIA GPUs using the transformers library (Wolf et al., 2020). Each model was trained with 10 random seeds.

F.2. Reasoning Model Hyperparameters

- **GPT-5 Nano**
 - Model version `gpt-5-nano-2025-08-07`
 - Effort: low
 - Verbosity: low
- **Gemini-3 Flash**
 - Model version `gemini-3-flash-preview`
 - Effort: low

F.3. Prompt for Reasoning Models

The prompt for the reasoning models is provided in Figure 13.

Below are definitions of two major dimensions of cross cultural variation in the world based on the World Value Survey developed by political scientists Ronald Inglehart and Christian Welzel:

Traditional values emphasize the importance of religion, parent-child ties, deference to authority and traditional family values. People who embrace these values also reject divorce, abortion, euthanasia and suicide. These societies have high levels of national pride and a nationalistic outlook.

Secular-rational values have the opposite preferences to the traditional values. These societies place less emphasis on religion, traditional family values and authority. Divorce, abortion, euthanasia and suicide are seen as relatively acceptable. (Suicide is not necessarily more common.)

Survival values place emphasis on economic and physical security. It is linked with a relatively ethnocentric outlook and low levels of trust and tolerance.

Self-expression values give high priority to environmental protection, growing tolerance of foreigners, gays and lesbians and gender equality, and rising demands for participation in decision-making in economic and political life.

These value axes form 4 cultural quadrants: Traditional, Survival; Traditional, Self-Expression; Secular, Survival; Secular, Self-Expression. How would a human annotator from each of the 4 cultural quadrants rate the item below: safe or unsafe? Try to emulate a subjective human judgement of how harmful this input is, pretending to be an annotator from each of these quadrants. Respond in JSON format: {"Traditional,Survival": "safe/unsafe", "Traditional,Self-Expression": "safe/unsafe", "Secular,Survival": "safe/unsafe", "Secular,Self-Expression": "safe/unsafe"}

{item}

Figure 13. Prompt for the reasoning LLM-as-a-Judge model to emulate judgments from the 4 cultural quadrants (Definitions of the values taken directly from www.worldvaluessurvey.org).

G. Hierarchical Linear Model Details

Table 21. Overview of all mixed-effects models fitted per dataset. Each row corresponds to one regression table included below.

Dataset	Model	Specification	Family	Table
CREHate	Null	Intercept + RE	GLMER (binomial)	22
CREHate	Demographics	+ ethnicity, age, gender	GLMER (binomial)	23
CREHate	Culture	+ cultural zone (nationality)	GLMER (binomial)	24
CREHate	Culture (Trad)	+ trad values	GLMER (binomial)	25
CREHate	Culture (Surv)	+ surv values	GLMER (binomial)	26
CREHate	Culture (Trad+Surv)	+ trad + surv values	GLMER (binomial)	27
CREHate	Culture (Trad*Surv)	+ trad × surv values	GLMER (binomial)	28
CREHate	Demog + Cult	+ demographics + culture (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	29
CREHate	Demog + Cult (Vals)	+ demographics + values (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	30
CREHate	Demog × Cult	+ demographics × culture (interaction)	GLMER (binomial)	31
CREHate	Demog × Cult (Vals)	+ demographics × values (interaction)	GLMER (binomial)	32
CREHate	Culture (Quadrants)	+ cultural quadrants (Inglehart-Welzel)	GLMER (binomial)	33
CREHate	Demog + Cult (Quadrants)	+ demographics + quadrants (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	34
<hr/>				
D3	Null	Intercept + RE	LMM	35
D3	Demographics	+ age, gender	LMM	36
D3	Culture	+ cultural zone (residence)	LMM	37
D3	Culture (Trad)	+ trad values	LMM	38
D3	Culture (Surv)	+ surv values	LMM	39
D3	Culture (Trad+Surv)	+ trad + surv values	LMM	40
D3	Culture (Trad*Surv)	+ trad × surv values	LMM	41
D3	Demog + Cult	+ demographics + culture (additive)	LMM	42
D3	Demog + Cult (Vals)	+ demographics + values (additive)	LMM	43
D3	Demog × Cult	+ demographics × culture (interaction)	LMM	44
D3	Demog × Cult (Vals)	+ demographics × values (interaction)	LMM	45
D3	Culture (Quadrants)	+ cultural quadrants (Inglehart-Welzel)	LMM	46
D3	Demog + Cult (Quadrants)	+ demographics + quadrants (additive)	LMM	47
<hr/>				
CultFrames	Null	Intercept + controls + RE	GLMER (binomial)	48
CultFrames	Demographics	+ age, gender	GLMER (binomial)	49
CultFrames	Culture	+ cultural zone (birth)	GLMER (binomial)	50
CultFrames	Culture (Trad)	+ trad values	GLMER (binomial)	51
CultFrames	Culture (Surv)	+ surv values	GLMER (binomial)	52
CultFrames	Culture (Trad+Surv)	+ trad + surv values	GLMER (binomial)	53
CultFrames	Culture (Trad*Surv)	+ trad × surv values	GLMER (binomial)	54
CultFrames	Demog + Cult	+ demographics + culture (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	55
CultFrames	Demog + Cult (Vals)	+ demographics + values (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	56
CultFrames	Demog × Cult	+ demographics × culture (interaction)	GLMER (binomial)	57
CultFrames	Demog × Cult (Vals)	+ demographics × values (interaction)	GLMER (binomial)	58
CultFrames	Culture (Quadrants)	+ cultural quadrants (Inglehart-Welzel)	GLMER (binomial)	59
CultFrames	Demog + Cult (Quadrants)	+ demographics + quadrants (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	60
<hr/>				
DICES Expert	Null	Intercept + controls + RE	GLMER (binomial)	62
DICES Expert	Demographics	+ ethnicity, age, gender	GLMER (binomial)	63
DICES Expert	Culture	+ cultural zone (locale)	GLMER (binomial)	64
DICES Expert	Culture (Trad)	+ trad values	GLMER (binomial)	65
DICES Expert	Culture (Surv)	+ surv values	GLMER (binomial)	66
DICES Expert	Culture (Trad+Surv)	+ trad + surv values	GLMER (binomial)	67
DICES Expert	Culture (Trad*Surv)	+ trad × surv values	GLMER (binomial)	68
DICES Expert	Demog + Cult	+ demographics + culture (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	69

continued on next page

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Dataset	Model	Specification	Family	Table
DICES Expert	Demog + Cult (Vals)	+ demographics + values (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	70
DICES Expert	Demog × Cult	+ demographics × culture (interaction)	GLMER (binomial)	71
DICES Expert	Demog × Cult (Vals)	+ demographics × values (interaction)	GLMER (binomial)	72
DICES Expert	Culture (Quadrants)	+ cultural quadrants (Inglehart-Welzel)	GLMER (binomial)	73
DICES Expert	Demog + Cult (Quadrants)	+ demographics + quadrants (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	74
DIVE	Null	Intercept + RE	LMM	75
DIVE	Demographics	+ ethnicity, age, gender	LMM	76
DIVE	Culture	+ cultural zone (birth)	LMM	77
DIVE	Culture (Trad)	+ trad values	LMM	78
DIVE	Culture (Surv)	+ surv values	LMM	79
DIVE	Culture (Trad+Surv)	+ trad + surv values	LMM	80
DIVE	Culture (Trad*Surv)	+ trad × surv values	LMM	81
DIVE	Demog + Cult	+ demographics + culture (additive)	LMM	82
DIVE	Demog + Cult (Vals)	+ demographics + values (additive)	LMM	83
DIVE	Demog × Cult	+ demographics × culture (interaction)	LMM	84
DIVE	Demog × Cult (Vals)	+ demographics × values (interaction)	LMM	85
DIVE	Culture (Quadrants)	+ cultural quadrants (Inglehart-Welzel)	LMM	86
DIVE	Demog + Cult (Quadrants)	+ demographics + quadrants (additive)	LMM	87
Severity	Null	Intercept + RE	LMM	88
Severity	Demographics	+ ethnicity, age, gender	LMM	89
Severity	Culture	+ cultural zone (residence)	LMM	90
Severity	Culture (Trad)	+ trad values	LMM	91
Severity	Culture (Surv)	+ surv values	LMM	92
Severity	Culture (Trad+Surv)	+ trad + surv values	LMM	93
Severity	Culture (Trad*Surv)	+ trad × surv values	LMM	94
Severity	Demog + Cult	+ demographics + culture (additive)	LMM	95
Severity	Demog + Cult (Vals)	+ demographics + values (additive)	LMM	96
Severity	Demog × Cult	+ demographics × culture (interaction)	LMM	97
Severity	Demog × Cult (Vals)	+ demographics × values (interaction)	LMM	98
Severity	Culture (Quadrants)	+ cultural quadrants (Inglehart-Welzel)	LMM	99
Severity	Demog + Cult (Quadrants)	+ demographics + quadrants (additive)	LMM	100
NLPositionality	Null	Intercept + RE	GLMER (binomial)	101
NLPositionality	Demographics	+ ethnicity, age, gender	GLMER (binomial)	102
NLPositionality	Culture	+ cultural zone	GLMER (binomial)	103
NLPositionality	Culture (Trad)	+ trad values	GLMER (binomial)	104
NLPositionality	Culture (Surv)	+ surv values	GLMER (binomial)	105
NLPositionality	Culture (Trad+Surv)	+ trad + surv values	GLMER (binomial)	106
NLPositionality	Culture (Trad*Surv)	+ trad × surv values	GLMER (binomial)	107
NLPositionality	Demog + Cult	+ demographics + culture (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	108
NLPositionality	Demog + Cult (Vals)	+ demographics + values (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	109
NLPositionality	Demog × Cult	+ demographics × culture (interaction)	GLMER (binomial)	110
NLPositionality	Demog × Cult (Vals)	+ demographics × values (interaction)	GLMER (binomial)	111
NLPositionality	Culture (Quadrants)	+ cultural quadrants (Inglehart-Welzel)	GLMER (binomial)	112
NLPositionality	Demog + Cult (Quadrants)	+ demographics + quadrants (additive)	GLMER (binomial)	113
PRISM	Null	Intercept + controls + RE	LMM	114
PRISM	Demographics	+ ethnicity, age, gender	LMM	115
PRISM	Culture	+ cultural zone (birth)	LMM	116
PRISM	Culture (Trad)	+ trad values	LMM	117
PRISM	Culture (Surv)	+ surv values	LMM	118

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Dataset	Model	Specification	Family	Table
PRISM	Culture (Trad+Surv)	+ trad + surv values	LMM	119
PRISM	Culture (Trad*Surv)	+ trad × surv values	LMM	120
PRISM	Demog + Cult	+ demographics + culture (additive)	LMM	121
PRISM	Demog + Cult (Vals)	+ demographics + values (additive)	LMM	122
PRISM	Demog × Cult	+ demographics × culture (interaction)	LMM	123
PRISM	Demog × Cult (Vals)	+ demographics × values (interaction)	LMM	124
PRISM	Culture (Quadrants)	+ cultural quadrants (Inglehart-Welzel)	LMM	125
PRISM	Demog + Cult (Quadrants)	+ demographics + quadrants (additive)	LMM	126

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.41 [-0.53; -0.30]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39042.36
BIC	39068.06
Log Likelihood	-19518.18
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.53

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 22. CREHate: Null model (GLMER, binomial)

Table 32. CREHate: Demographics x selected culture-values interaction (add) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * (nat_TradAgg + nat_SurvSAgg) + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.87 [-1.27; -0.46]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	0.53 [0.13; 0.93]*
rater_ethnicityBlack	0.57 [-0.10; 1.25]
rater_ethnicityMiddle_Eastern	0.74 [-1.52; 2.99]
rater_ethnicityMixed	-0.03 [-1.07; 1.01]
rater_age_groupboomer	0.31 [-0.22; 0.84]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.03 [-0.44; 0.51]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.10 [-0.11; 0.32]
rater_genderfemale	0.10 [-0.10; 0.30]
rater_gendernon-binary	0.46 [-0.45; 1.36]
nat_TradAgg	-0.08 [-0.58; 0.41]
nat_SurvSAgg	0.20 [-0.11; 0.51]
rater_ethnicityAsian:nat_TradAgg	0.32 [-0.65; 1.29]
rater_ethnicityBlack:nat_TradAgg	1.28 [-0.51; 3.06]
rater_ethnicityMiddle_Eastern:nat_TradAgg	-0.86 [-6.09; 4.36]
rater_ethnicityMixed:nat_TradAgg	-0.31 [-2.54; 1.92]
rater_ethnicityAsian:nat_SurvSAgg	-0.40 [-0.75; -0.05]*
rater_ethnicityBlack:nat_SurvSAgg	-0.84 [-1.75; 0.07]
rater_ethnicityMiddle_Eastern:nat_SurvSAgg	0.02 [-2.18; 2.22]
rater_ethnicityMixed:nat_SurvSAgg	0.16 [-1.00; 1.31]
rater_age_groupboomer:nat_TradAgg	0.06 [-0.87; 0.98]
rater_age_groupgenx:nat_TradAgg	0.45 [-0.23; 1.13]
rater_age_groupgenz:nat_TradAgg	0.12 [-0.51; 0.74]
rater_age_groupboomer:nat_SurvSAgg	-0.18 [-0.67; 0.30]
rater_age_groupgenx:nat_SurvSAgg	-0.23 [-0.63; 0.16]
rater_age_groupgenz:nat_SurvSAgg	-0.07 [-0.33; 0.20]
rater_genderfemale:nat_TradAgg	-0.03 [-0.52; 0.46]
rater_gendernon-binary:nat_TradAgg	0.65 [-1.50; 2.80]
rater_genderfemale:nat_SurvSAgg	0.09 [-0.13; 0.32]
rater_gendernon-binary:nat_SurvSAgg	-0.34 [-1.29; 0.61]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39043.42
BIC	39317.48
Log Likelihood	-19489.71
Num. obs.	38727

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Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

CREHate (continued)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * (nat_TradAgg + nat_SurvSAgg) + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.48

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = male.

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.51 [-0.66; -0.36]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	0.08 [-0.07; 0.23]
rater_ethnicityBlack	-0.22 [-0.38; -0.06]*
rater_ethnicityMiddle_Eastern	0.36 [-0.36; 1.08]
rater_ethnicityMixed	0.02 [-0.40; 0.43]
rater_age_groupboomer	0.01 [-0.21; 0.24]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.14 [-0.30; 0.01]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.08 [-0.06; 0.21]
rater_genderfemale	0.24 [0.13; 0.35]*
rater_gendernon-binary	0.23 [-0.23; 0.70]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39026.74
BIC	39129.51
Log Likelihood	-19501.37
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.50

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = male.

Table 23. CREHate: Demographics model (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ con_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.44 [-0.56; -0.31]*
con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.08 [-0.04; 0.20]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39042.74
BIC	39077.00
Log Likelihood	-19517.37
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.52

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: con_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 24. CREHate: Culture model (GLMER, binomial)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ TradAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.46 [-0.59; -0.34]*
nat_TradAgg	0.12 [0.01; 0.24]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39040.21
BIC	39074.47
Log Likelihood	-19516.11
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.52

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 25. CREHate: Culture values (TradAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.43 [-0.57; -0.29]*
nat_SurvSAgg	0.01 [-0.05; 0.06]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39044.26
BIC	39078.51
Log Likelihood	-19518.13
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.53

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 26. CREHate: Culture values (SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ TradAgg + SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.35 [-0.50; -0.21]*
nat_TradAgg	0.45 [0.21; 0.69]*
nat_SurvSAgg	-0.17 [-0.28; -0.06]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39033.23
BIC	39076.05
Log Likelihood	-19511.62
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.51

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 27. CREHate: Culture values (TradAgg + SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ TradAgg * SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.36 [-0.51; -0.20]*
nat_TradAgg	0.44 [-0.09; 0.96]
nat_SurvSAgg	-0.17 [-0.28; -0.06]*
nat_TradAgg:nat_SurvSAgg	0.01 [-0.23; 0.25]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39035.23
BIC	39086.61
Log Likelihood	-19511.61
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.51

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 28. CREHate: Culture values (TradAgg * SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + con_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.52 [-0.67; -0.37]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	-0.07 [-0.25; 0.11]
rater_ethnicityBlack	-0.42 [-0.64; -0.20]*
rater_ethnicityMiddle_Eastern	0.33 [-0.38; 1.05]
rater_ethnicityMixed	-0.05 [-0.46; 0.37]
rater_age_groupboomer	0.01 [-0.22; 0.23]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.14 [-0.29; 0.02]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.06 [-0.07; 0.20]
rater_genderfemale	0.25 [0.14; 0.36]*
rater_gendernon-binary	0.25 [-0.22; 0.71]
con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.25 [0.07; 0.43]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39021.61
BIC	39132.95
Log Likelihood	-19497.81
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.49

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = male; con_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 29. CREHate: Demographics + Culture additive (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + nat_TradAgg + nat_SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.42 [-0.64; -0.20]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	0.02 [-0.16; 0.19]
rater_ethnicityBlack	-0.20 [-0.41; 0.01]
rater_ethnicityMiddle_Eastern	0.41 [-0.31; 1.13]
rater_ethnicityMixed	0.01 [-0.40; 0.42]
rater_age_groupboomer	0.01 [-0.21; 0.23]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.15 [-0.30; 0.00]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.07 [-0.06; 0.20]
rater_genderfemale	0.23 [0.12; 0.34]*
rater_gendernon-binary	0.23 [-0.23; 0.70]
nat_TradAgg	0.36 [0.10; 0.61]*
nat_SurvSAgg	-0.16 [-0.28; -0.03]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39023.12
BIC	39143.02
Log Likelihood	-19497.56
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.49

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = male.

Table 30. CREHate: Demographics + selected culture-values additive (add) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * con_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.54 [-0.69; -0.38]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	-0.14 [-0.36; 0.08]
rater_ethnicityBlack	-0.36 [-0.75; 0.03]
rater_ethnicityMiddle_Eastern	0.26 [-0.53; 1.05]
rater_ethnicityMixed	0.14 [-0.35; 0.63]
rater_age_groupboomer	-0.04 [-0.28; 0.20]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.14 [-0.31; 0.02]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.10 [-0.08; 0.28]
rater_genderfemale	0.28 [0.15; 0.41]*
rater_gendernon-binary	0.20 [-0.34; 0.75]
con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.21 [-0.23; 0.64]
rater_ethnicityAsian:con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.20 [-0.27; 0.68]
rater_ethnicityBlack:con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.05 [-0.52; 0.63]
rater_ethnicityMiddle_Eastern:con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.35 [-1.51; 2.22]
rater_ethnicityMixed:con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.58 [-1.55; 0.39]
rater_age_groupboomer:con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.34 [-0.29; 0.96]
rater_age_groupgenx:con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.05 [-0.49; 0.58]
rater_age_groupgenz:con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.07 [-0.34; 0.20]
rater_genderfemale:con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.13 [-0.37; 0.11]
rater_gendernon-binary:con_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.13 [-0.90; 1.17]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39033.48
BIC	39221.90
Log Likelihood	-19494.74
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.49

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = male; con_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 31. CREHate: Demographics x Culture interaction (GLMER, binomial)

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	harmful ~ nat_quadrant + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.44 [-0.56; -0.31]*
nat_quadrantII	0.28 [0.11; 0.44]*
nat_quadrantIV	-0.06 [-0.20; 0.09]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39034.28
BIC	39077.10
Log Likelihood	-19512.14
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.51

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: nat_quadrant = I.

Table 33. CREHate: Culture quadrants (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + nat_quadrant + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-0.52 [-0.66; -0.37]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	-0.14 [-0.35; 0.07]
rater_ethnicityBlack	-0.33 [-0.59; -0.08]*
rater_ethnicityMiddle_Eastern	0.35 [-0.37; 1.06]
rater_ethnicityMixed	-0.02 [-0.43; 0.40]
rater_age_groupboomer	0.00 [-0.22; 0.22]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.14 [-0.29; 0.01]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.07 [-0.07; 0.20]
rater_genderfemale	0.24 [0.13; 0.35]*
rater_gendernon-binary	0.26 [-0.20; 0.73]
nat_quadrantII	0.36 [0.11; 0.60]*
nat_quadrantIV	0.14 [-0.10; 0.38]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.59
AIC	39021.91
BIC	39141.81
Log Likelihood	-19496.96
Num. obs.	38727
Num. groups: item_id	1580
Num. groups: rater_id	1037
Var: item_id (Intercept)	4.29
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.49

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = male; nat_quadrant = I.

Table 34. CREHate: Demographics + Quadrants additive (GLMER, binomial)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.01 [0.50; 1.53]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	429107.78
BIC	429166.85
Log Likelihood	-214547.89
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.43
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 35. D3: Null model (LMM)

Table 44. D3: Demographics x Culture interaction (LMM)

	harmful ~ (age + gender) * cor_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.83 [0.31; 1.36]*
rater_age_group30-50	-0.20 [-0.28; -0.12]*
rater_age_group50+	-0.11 [-0.20; -0.02]*
rater_genderOther	0.23 [-0.11; 0.57]
rater_genderWoman	0.26 [0.19; 0.33]*
cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.32 [0.22; 0.42]*
cor_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.16 [-0.06; 0.38]
cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.29 [0.16; 0.41]*
cor_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.12 [-0.05; 0.29]
cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.28 [0.17; 0.39]*
rater_age_group30-50:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.25 [0.12; 0.38]*
rater_age_group50+:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.44 [0.27; 0.60]*
rater_age_group30-50:cor_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.09 [-0.14; 0.31]
rater_age_group50+:cor_cultural_zoneConfucian	-0.23 [-0.48; 0.02]
rater_age_group30-50:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.26 [0.11; 0.41]*
rater_age_group50+:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.19 [-0.00; 0.38]
rater_age_group30-50:cor_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.24 [0.02; 0.47]*
rater_age_group50+:cor_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.07 [-0.17; 0.31]
rater_age_group30-50:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.19 [0.06; 0.33]*
rater_age_group50+:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.04 [-0.20; 0.12]
rater_genderOther:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.39 [-0.99; 0.21]
rater_genderWoman:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.31 [-0.43; -0.19]*
rater_genderWoman:cor_cultural_zoneConfucian	-0.54 [-0.70; -0.37]*
rater_genderOther:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.29 [-1.11; 0.53]
rater_genderWoman:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.20 [-0.33; -0.06]*
rater_genderOther:cor_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-0.16 [-0.91; 0.58]
rater_genderWoman:cor_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-0.07 [-0.26; 0.12]
rater_genderOther:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.91 [-1.42; -0.40]*
rater_genderWoman:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.33 [-0.45; -0.21]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02

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D3 (continued)

	harmful ~ (age + gender) * cor_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	428902.45
BIC	429237.14
Log Likelihood	-214417.23
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.40
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = 18-30; rater_gender = Man; cor_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 45. D3: Demographics x selected culture-values interaction (inter) (LMM)

	harmful ~ (age + gender) * (cor_TrAdAgg * cor_SurvSAgg) + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.14 [0.62; 1.66]*
rater_age_group30-50	-0.12 [-0.20; -0.05]*
rater_age_group50+	-0.21 [-0.31; -0.12]*
rater_genderOther	-0.54 [-1.00; -0.09]*
rater_genderWoman	-0.10 [-0.16; -0.03]*
cor_TrAdAgg	0.06 [-0.01; 0.13]
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.11 [-0.16; -0.07]*
cor_TrAdAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.04 [-0.08; 0.00]
rater_age_group30-50:cor_TrAdAgg	-0.10 [-0.18; -0.01]*
rater_age_group50+:cor_TrAdAgg	-0.12 [-0.23; -0.02]*
rater_age_group30-50:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.02 [-0.07; 0.04]
rater_age_group50+:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.05 [-0.11; 0.01]
rater_genderOther:cor_TrAdAgg	-0.15 [-0.73; 0.42]
rater_genderWoman:cor_TrAdAgg	-0.08 [-0.16; -0.01]*
rater_genderOther:cor_SurvSAgg	0.18 [-0.09; 0.46]
rater_genderWoman:cor_SurvSAgg	0.11 [0.07; 0.16]*
rater_age_group30-50:cor_TrAdAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.04 [-0.01; 0.09]
rater_age_group50+:cor_TrAdAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.18 [0.11; 0.24]*
rater_genderOther:cor_TrAdAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.25 [0.02; 0.48]*
rater_genderWoman:cor_TrAdAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.08 [0.03; 0.12]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	428973.66
BIC	429219.75
Log Likelihood	-214461.83
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.41
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = 18-30; rater_gender = Man.

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ age + gender + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.06 [0.55; 1.58]*
rater_age_group30-50	-0.12 [-0.16; -0.07]*
rater_age_group50+	-0.12 [-0.17; -0.06]*
rater_genderOther	-0.21 [-0.42; 0.01]
rater_genderWoman	0.03 [-0.02; 0.07]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	429101.26
BIC	429199.70
Log Likelihood	-214540.63
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.43
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = 18-30; rater_gender = Man.

Table 36. D3: Demographics model (LMM)

	harmful ~ cor_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.89 [0.37; 1.41]*
cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.30 [0.24; 0.36]*
cor_cultural_zoneConfucian	-0.19 [-0.27; -0.11]*
cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.29 [0.22; 0.36]*
cor_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.16 [0.07; 0.25]*
cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.15 [0.09; 0.21]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	428936.57
BIC	429044.85
Log Likelihood	-214457.29
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.41
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cor_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 37. D3: Culture model (LMM)

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	harmful ~ TradAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.01 [0.49; 1.52]*
cor_TradAgg	-0.11 [-0.13; -0.09]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	429027.93
BIC	429096.84
Log Likelihood	-214506.97
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.42
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 38. D3: Culture values (TradAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.06 [0.55; 1.58]*
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.07 [-0.09; -0.06]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	429011.57
BIC	429080.48
Log Likelihood	-214498.79
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.42
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 39. D3: Culture values (SurvSAgg) (LMM)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ TradAgg + SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.05 [0.53; 1.56]*
cor_TradAgg	-0.04 [-0.08; -0.00]*
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.05 [-0.08; -0.03]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	429014.90
BIC	429093.65
Log Likelihood	-214499.45
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.42
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 40. D3: Culture values (TradAgg + SurvSAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ TradAgg * SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.01 [0.49; 1.52]*
cor_TradAgg	-0.04 [-0.08; -0.01]*
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.06 [-0.09; -0.04]*
cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.05 [0.02; 0.07]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	429009.04
BIC	429097.63
Log Likelihood	-214495.52
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.42
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 41. D3: Culture values (TradAgg * SurvSAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ age + gender + cor_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.88 [0.36; 1.40]*
rater_age_group30-50	-0.05 [-0.10; -0.00]*
rater_age_group50+	-0.03 [-0.09; 0.03]
rater_genderOther	-0.16 [-0.37; 0.05]
rater_genderWoman	0.07 [0.02; 0.11]*
cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.30 [0.24; 0.36]*
cor_cultural_zoneConfucian	-0.18 [-0.26; -0.09]*
cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.29 [0.22; 0.36]*
cor_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.16 [0.07; 0.25]*
cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.16 [0.10; 0.22]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	428946.21
BIC	429093.86
Log Likelihood	-214458.10
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.41
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = 18-30; rater_gender = Man; cor_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 42. D3: Demographics + Culture additive (LMM)

	harmful ~ age + gender + cor_TradAgg * cor_SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.02 [0.51; 1.54]*
rater_age_group30-50	-0.08 [-0.13; -0.04]*
rater_age_group50+	-0.07 [-0.13; -0.01]*
rater_genderOther	-0.15 [-0.36; 0.06]
rater_genderWoman	0.06 [0.02; 0.10]*
cor_TradAgg	-0.03 [-0.07; 0.01]
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.07 [-0.09; -0.04]*
cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.04 [0.02; 0.07]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	429010.46
BIC	429138.43
Log Likelihood	-214492.23
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.42
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = 18-30; rater_gender = Man.

Table 43. D3: Demographics + selected culture-values additive (inter) (LMM)

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	harmful ~ cor_quadrant + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.92 [0.40; 1.44]*
cor_quadrantII	-0.24 [-0.32; -0.17]*
cor_quadrantIII	0.27 [0.22; 0.31]*
cor_quadrantIV	0.12 [0.06; 0.19]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	428914.64
BIC	429003.24
Log Likelihood	-214448.32
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.41
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cor_quadrant = I.

Table 46. D3: Culture quadrants (LMM)

	harmful ~ age + gender + cor_quadrant + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/subtopic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.91 [0.39; 1.43]*
rater_age_group30-50	-0.05 [-0.10; -0.00]*
rater_age_group50+	-0.04 [-0.10; 0.01]
rater_genderOther	-0.14 [-0.35; 0.07]
rater_genderWoman	0.07 [0.03; 0.11]*
cor_quadrantII	-0.23 [-0.31; -0.16]*
cor_quadrantIII	0.27 [0.22; 0.31]*
cor_quadrantIV	0.12 [0.06; 0.19]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	428922.77
BIC	429050.74
Log Likelihood	-214448.39
Num. obs.	139184
Num. groups: item_id:subtopic:topic	4590
Num. groups: rater_id	4075
Num. groups: subtopic:topic	11
Num. groups: topic	3
Var: item_id:subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.22
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.41
Var: subtopic:topic (Intercept)	0.01
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.20
Var: Residual	1.11

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = 18-30; rater_gender = Man; cor_quadrant = I.

Table 47. D3: Demographics + Quadrants additive (LMM)

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	harmful ~ category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.37 [-3.68; -3.06]*
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.21; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.02 [-0.27; 0.23]
categorygreetings	0.21 [-0.03; 0.45]
categoryreligion	-0.05 [-0.29; 0.20]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.44; 0.88]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6595.11
BIC	6667.14
Log Likelihood	-3287.56
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.74
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.68

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 48. CultFrames: Null model (GLMER, binomial)

Table 57. CultFrames: Demographics x Culture interaction (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ (age + gender) * cob_cult_cluster + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-4.07 [-5.25; -2.90]*
rater_age_groupboomer	1.34 [-2.44; 5.11]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.73 [-2.43; 0.97]
rater_age_groupgenz	-0.38 [-1.92; 1.15]
rater_genderFemale	0.27 [-1.04; 1.58]
cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	2.56 [1.06; 4.06]*
cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.96 [-0.72; 2.63]
cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.01 [-1.48; 1.49]
cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.07 [-1.65; 1.79]
cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.32 [-1.13; 1.76]
cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.15 [-1.13; 1.44]
categoryetiquette	-0.02 [-0.22; 0.18]
categoryfamily	-0.03 [-0.27; 0.22]
categorygreetings	0.22 [-0.01; 0.45]
categoryreligion	-0.03 [-0.27; 0.21]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.28; 0.70]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.96]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.45; 0.87]*
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	1.00 [-1.58; 3.59]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.73 [-2.74; 1.28]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.04 [-2.71; 2.79]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.69 [-1.40; 2.79]
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	15.22 [-552.38; 582.82]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	1.81 [-0.15; 3.76]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.60 [-1.21; 2.40]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	1.14 [-1.23; 3.51]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.84 [-1.30; 2.97]
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-0.50 [-5.26; 4.27]

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CultFrames (continued)

	harmful ~ (age + gender) * cob_cult_cluster + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.67 [-1.65; 2.99]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.74 [-1.16; 2.64]
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-1.37 [-5.66; 2.92]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.86 [-1.17; 2.90]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.48 [-1.19; 2.15]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.39 [-1.40; 2.19]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	-0.90 [-2.85; 1.04]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	1.32 [-0.24; 2.89]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.27 [-1.57; 2.11]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.19 [-1.53; 1.90]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.06 [-1.52; 1.40]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.14
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6568.48
BIC	6863.79
Log Likelihood	-3243.24
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.77
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	1.87

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; cob_cultural_zone = English-Speaking; category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 58. CultFrames: Demographics x selected culture-values interaction (inter) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ (age + gender) * (cob_TrAdAgg * cob_SurvSAgg) + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.85 [-4.36; -3.34]*
rater_age_groupboomer	4.39 [-10.53; 19.32]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.37 [-0.37; 1.12]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.16 [-0.33; 0.66]
rater_genderFemale	0.65 [0.17; 1.12]*
cob_TrAdAgg	-0.82 [-1.78; 0.13]
cob_SurvSAgg	-0.66 [-1.27; -0.05]*
categoryetiquette	-0.02 [-0.22; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.02 [-0.27; 0.23]
categorygreetings	0.22 [-0.02; 0.46]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.21]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.45; 0.88]*
cob_TrAdAgg:cob_SurvSAgg	1.21 [0.42; 2.01]*
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_TrAdAgg	17.23 [-35.86; 70.33]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_TrAdAgg	1.07 [-0.35; 2.49]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_TrAdAgg	0.48 [-0.59; 1.56]
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_SurvSAgg	-3.96 [-29.74; 21.82]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_SurvSAgg	-0.54 [-1.53; 0.45]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_SurvSAgg	0.45 [-0.33; 1.22]
rater_genderFemale:cob_TrAdAgg	1.44 [0.46; 2.42]*
rater_genderFemale:cob_SurvSAgg	-0.86 [-1.55; -0.17]*
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_TrAdAgg:cob_SurvSAgg	-5.09 [-31.91; 21.73]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_TrAdAgg:cob_SurvSAgg	-0.38 [-1.78; 1.01]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_TrAdAgg:cob_SurvSAgg	-0.76 [-1.72; 0.21]
rater_genderFemale:cob_TrAdAgg:cob_SurvSAgg	-0.05 [-0.94; 0.85]

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CultFrames (continued)

	harmful ~ (age + gender) * (cob_TrAdAgg * cob_SurvSAgg) + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.12
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6563.65
BIC	6772.53
Log Likelihood	-3252.83
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.77
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.01

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 61. CultFrames: Demographics x Quadrants interaction (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ (age + gender) * cob_quadrant + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.76 [-4.45; -3.07]*
rater_age_groupboomer	2.31 [0.25; 4.36]*
rater_age_groupgenx	0.47 [-0.39; 1.34]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.00 [-0.88; 0.89]
rater_genderFemale	0.44 [-0.28; 1.16]
cob_quadrantII	-0.21 [-1.23; 0.82]
cob_quadrantIII	0.64 [-0.29; 1.56]
cob_quadrantIV	-0.13 [-1.17; 0.91]
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.21; 0.20]
categoryfamily	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.21]
categorygreetings	0.22 [-0.02; 0.46]
categoryreligion	-0.05 [-0.29; 0.20]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.49; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.44; 0.88]*
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_quadrantII	0.64 [-1.06; 2.34]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_quadrantII	0.28 [-0.98; 1.53]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_quadrantIII	-0.74 [-2.14; 0.65]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_quadrantIII	-0.40 [-1.62; 0.81]
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_quadrantIV	-2.15 [-5.13; 0.83]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_quadrantIV	-0.50 [-2.14; 1.14]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_quadrantIV	0.17 [-1.07; 1.41]
rater_genderFemale:cob_quadrantII	1.03 [-0.08; 2.15]
rater_genderFemale:cob_quadrantIII	0.25 [-0.80; 1.30]
rater_genderFemale:cob_quadrantIV	-0.63 [-1.73; 0.47]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.06
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6592.65
BIC	6787.12
Log Likelihood	-3269.32
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.75
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.35

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; cob_quadrant = I; category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

	harmful ~ age + gender + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.67 [-4.10; -3.23]*
rater_age_groupboomer	0.71 [-0.77; 2.18]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.28 [-0.28; 0.85]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.04 [-0.40; 0.48]
rater_genderFemale	0.46 [0.06; 0.86]*
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.21; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.02 [-0.27; 0.23]
categorygreetings	0.22 [-0.02; 0.46]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.20]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.44; 0.88]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.51
AIC	6596.07
BIC	6696.90
Log Likelihood	-3284.03
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.74
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.56

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 49. CultFrames: Demographics model (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ cob_cult_cluster + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-4.20 [-4.92; -3.48]*
cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	2.55 [1.63; 3.47]*
cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.85 [-0.11; 1.82]
cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	1.61 [0.82; 2.40]*
cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.66 [-0.27; 1.60]
cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.70 [-0.16; 1.56]
cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.37 [-0.38; 1.12]
categoryetiquette	-0.02 [-0.22; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.22]
categorygreetings	0.21 [-0.03; 0.45]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.21]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.49; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.45; 0.88]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.09
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6553.49
BIC	6668.73
Log Likelihood	-3260.74
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.76
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.18

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cob_cultural_zone = English-Speaking; category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 50. CultFrames: Culture model (GLMER, binomial)

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	harmful ~ cob_TradAgg + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.42 [-3.74; -3.10]*
cob_TradAgg	0.22 [-0.09; 0.53]
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.21; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.03 [-0.28; 0.22]
categorygreetings	0.21 [-0.03; 0.45]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.20]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.45; 0.88]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6595.14
BIC	6674.37
Log Likelihood	-3286.57
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.74
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.68

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 51. CultFrames: Culture values (TradAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ cob_SurvSAgg + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.25 [-3.58; -2.93]*
cob_SurvSAgg	-0.23 [-0.43; -0.02]*
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.21; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.02 [-0.27; 0.23]
categorygreetings	0.21 [-0.03; 0.45]
categoryreligion	-0.05 [-0.29; 0.20]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.44; 0.88]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.51
AIC	6592.40
BIC	6671.63
Log Likelihood	-3285.20
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.74
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.60

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 52. CultFrames: Culture values (SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ cob_TradAgg + cob_SurvSAgg + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.21 [-3.53; -2.90]*
cob_TradAgg	0.99 [0.55; 1.42]*
cob_SurvSAgg	-0.72 [-1.01; -0.42]*
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.22; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.03 [-0.28; 0.23]
categorygreetings	0.21 [-0.03; 0.45]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.20]
model_nameipt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimageegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.45; 0.88]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.05
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6574.73
BIC	6661.16
Log Likelihood	-3275.36
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.75
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.44

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 53. CultFrames: Culture values (TradAgg + SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ cob_TradAgg * cob_SurvSAgg + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.40 [-3.73; -3.06]*
cob_TradAgg	0.53 [0.04; 1.03]*
cob_SurvSAgg	-1.08 [-1.43; -0.72]*
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.22; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.03 [-0.28; 0.22]
categorygreetings	0.21 [-0.03; 0.45]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.20]
model_nameept-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.45; 0.88]*
cob_TradAgg:cob_SurvSAgg	0.80 [0.34; 1.26]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.07
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6565.23
BIC	6658.87
Log Likelihood	-3269.62
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.76
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.31

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 54. CultFrames: Culture values (TradAgg * SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ age + gender + cob_cult_cluster + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-4.47 [-5.24; -3.70]*
rater_age_groupboomer	1.05 [-0.34; 2.43]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.17 [-0.37; 0.70]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.03 [-0.38; 0.44]
rater_genderFemale	0.38 [-0.00; 0.76]
cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	2.59 [1.68; 3.50]*
cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.95 [0.00; 1.90]*
cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	1.58 [0.79; 2.36]*
cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.76 [-0.17; 1.69]
cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.78 [-0.07; 1.63]
cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.41 [-0.33; 1.15]
categoryetiquette	-0.02 [-0.22; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.03 [-0.28; 0.22]
categorygreetings	0.22 [-0.03; 0.46]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.28; 0.21]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.44; 0.88]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.10
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6554.88
BIC	6698.93
Log Likelihood	-3257.44
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.76
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.08

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; cob_cultural_zone = English-Speaking; category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 55. CultFrames: Demographics + Culture additive (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ age + gender + cob_TradAgg * cob_SurvSAgg + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.64 [-4.09; -3.19]*
rater_age_groupboomer	0.84 [-0.58; 2.25]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.07 [-0.48; 0.62]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.04 [-0.38; 0.46]
rater_genderFemale	0.42 [0.04; 0.80]*
cob_TradAgg	0.49 [-0.00; 0.98]
cob_SurvSAgg	-1.06 [-1.41; -0.71]*
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.22; 0.19]
categoryfamily	-0.02 [-0.27; 0.23]
categorygreetings	0.21 [-0.03; 0.45]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.21]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.74 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.45; 0.88]*
cob_TradAgg:cob_SurvSAgg	0.81 [0.36; 1.27]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.08
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6566.84
BIC	6689.28
Log Likelihood	-3266.42
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.76
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.21

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 56. CultFrames: Demographics + selected culture-values additive (inter) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ cob_quadrant + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.38 [-3.82; -2.94]*
cob_quadrantII	0.38 [-0.20; 0.96]
cob_quadrantIII	0.31 [-0.23; 0.86]
cob_quadrantIV	-0.60 [-1.16; -0.03]*
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.21; 0.20]
categoryfamily	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.21]
categorygreetings	0.21 [-0.03; 0.45]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.20]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.49; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.45; 0.88]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.03
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6588.06
BIC	6681.69
Log Likelihood	-3281.03
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.74
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.62

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cob_quadrant = I; category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 59. CultFrames: Culture quadrants (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ age + gender + cob_quadrant + category + model_name + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	-3.73 [-4.26; -3.20]*
rater_age_groupboomer	1.04 [-0.44; 2.51]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.26 [-0.31; 0.83]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.03 [-0.41; 0.47]
rater_genderFemale	0.54 [0.14; 0.94]*
cob_quadrantII	0.43 [-0.15; 1.00]
cob_quadrantIII	0.38 [-0.16; 0.92]
cob_quadrantIV	-0.64 [-1.20; -0.07]*
categoryetiquette	-0.01 [-0.21; 0.20]
categoryfamily	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.21]
categorygreetings	0.22 [-0.03; 0.46]
categoryreligion	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.20]
model_namegpt-image	0.49 [0.27; 0.71]*
model_nameimagegen3	0.73 [0.50; 0.97]*
model_nameSD35	0.66 [0.45; 0.88]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.04
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.52
AIC	6585.95
BIC	6708.39
Log Likelihood	-3275.97
Num. obs.	9922
Num. groups: item_id	3577
Num. groups: rater_id	379
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.74
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.47

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; cob_quadrant = I; category = dates-of-significance; model_name = flux.

Table 60. CultFrames: Demographics + Quadrants additive (GLMER, binomial)

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	harmful ~ degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-1.71 [-2.18; -1.24]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.14 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.22 [0.79; 1.65]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.62; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.04
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.62
AIC	12393.61
BIC	12446.92
Log Likelihood	-6189.80
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.05
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.54
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.57

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 62. DICES Expert: Null model (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-2.78 [-3.66; -1.89]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	0.96 [-0.89; 2.82]
rater_ethnicityAsian/Asian subcontinent	0.87 [0.01; 1.74]*
rater_ethnicityBlack/African American	0.66 [-0.65; 1.96]
rater_ethnicityLatinX, Latino, Hispanic or Spanish Origin	0.10 [-1.07; 1.27]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern or North African	1.55 [-0.44; 3.54]
rater_ethnicityMixed	1.97 [-1.72; 5.67]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander	3.02 [0.35; 5.69]*
rater_age_groupgen x+	1.27 [0.75; 1.79]*
rater_age_groupgen z	0.39 [-0.57; 1.36]
rater_gendernonbinary	-1.03 [-3.81; 1.75]
rater_genderwoman	0.09 [-0.60; 0.79]
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.15 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.23 [0.80; 1.66]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.62; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.09
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.64
AIC	12382.47
BIC	12519.56
Log Likelihood	-6173.24
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.06
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.55
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.31

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 63. DICES Expert: Demographics model (GLMER, binomial)

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	harmful ~ cultural_cluster + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-2.07 [-2.60; -1.55]*
cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	1.05 [0.35; 1.75]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.14 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.22 [0.79; 1.65]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.61; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.06
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.62
AIC	12387.38
BIC	12448.30
Log Likelihood	-6185.69
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.05
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.54
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.30

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cor_cultural_zone = English-Speaking; degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 64. DICES Expert: Culture model (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ TradAgg + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-1.82 [-2.28; -1.35]*
cor_TradAgg	-1.77 [-2.96; -0.59]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.14 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.22 [0.79; 1.65]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.61; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.06
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.62
AIC	12387.38
BIC	12448.30
Log Likelihood	-6185.69
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.05
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.54
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.30

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 65. DICES Expert: Culture values (TradAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ SurvSAgg + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-1.16 [-1.75; -0.58]*
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.65 [-1.08; -0.21]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.14 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.22 [0.79; 1.65]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.61; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.06
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.62
AIC	12387.38
BIC	12448.30
Log Likelihood	-6185.69
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.05
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.54
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.30

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 66. DICES Expert: Culture values (SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ TradAgg + SurvSAgg + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-1.82 [-2.28; -1.35]*
cor_TradAgg	-1.77 [-2.96; -0.59]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.14 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.22 [0.79; 1.65]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.61; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.06
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.62
AIC	12387.38
BIC	12448.30
Log Likelihood	-6185.69
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.05
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.54
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.30

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 67. DICES Expert: Culture values (TradAgg + SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ TradAgg * SurvSAgg + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-1.82 [-2.28; -1.35]*
cor_TradAgg	-1.77 [-2.96; -0.59]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.14 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.22 [0.79; 1.65]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.61; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.06
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.62
AIC	12387.38
BIC	12448.30
Log Likelihood	-6185.69
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.05
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.54
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.30

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 68. DICES Expert: Culture values (TradAgg * SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cultural_cluster + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-2.80 [-3.67; -1.94]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	0.98 [-0.82; 2.77]
rater_ethnicityAsian/Asian subcontinent	-0.56 [-1.85; 0.73]
rater_ethnicityBlack/African American	0.66 [-0.60; 1.93]
rater_ethnicityLatinX, Latino, Hispanic or Spanish Origin	0.09 [-1.05; 1.22]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern or North African	1.59 [-0.33; 3.52]
rater_ethnicityMixed	1.91 [-1.67; 5.48]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander	2.96 [0.37; 5.55]*
rater_age_groupgen x+	1.25 [0.74; 1.77]*
rater_age_groupgen z	0.29 [-0.65; 1.23]
rater_gendernonbinary	-0.95 [-3.64; 1.74]
rater_genderwoman	0.18 [-0.50; 0.86]
cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	1.80 [0.56; 3.03]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.15 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.23 [0.80; 1.66]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.62; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.11
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.63
AIC	12376.62
BIC	12521.32
Log Likelihood	-6169.31
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.06
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.55
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.09

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; cor_cultural_zone = English-Speaking; degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 69. DICES Expert: Demographics + Culture additive (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cor_SurvSAgg + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-1.24 [-2.60; 0.11]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	0.98 [-0.82; 2.77]
rater_ethnicityAsian/Asian subcontinent	-0.56 [-1.85; 0.73]
rater_ethnicityBlack/African American	0.66 [-0.60; 1.93]
rater_ethnicityLatinX, Latino, Hispanic or Spanish Origin	0.09 [-1.05; 1.22]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern or North African	1.59 [-0.33; 3.52]
rater_ethnicityMixed	1.91 [-1.67; 5.48]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander	2.96 [0.37; 5.55]*
rater_age_groupgen x+	1.25 [0.74; 1.77]*
rater_age_groupgen z	0.29 [-0.65; 1.23]
rater_gendernonbinary	-0.95 [-3.64; 1.74]
rater_genderwoman	0.18 [-0.50; 0.86]
cor_SurvSAgg	-1.11 [-1.87; -0.35]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.15 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.23 [0.80; 1.66]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.62; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.11
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.63
AIC	12376.62
BIC	12521.32
Log Likelihood	-6169.31
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.06
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.55
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.09

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 70. DICES Expert: Demographics + selected culture-values additive (surv) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * cultural_cluster + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-2.70 [-3.59; -1.81]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	0.97 [-0.79; 2.73]
rater_ethnicityAsian/Asian subcontinent	-0.48 [-1.75; 0.78]
rater_ethnicityBlack/African American	0.63 [-0.61; 1.87]
rater_ethnicityLatinX, Latino, Hispanic or Spanish Origin	0.20 [-0.91; 1.31]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern or North African	1.50 [-0.39; 3.39]
rater_ethnicityMixed	2.26 [-1.25; 5.76]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander	3.31 [0.76; 5.85]*
rater_age_groupgen x+	1.53 [0.96; 2.10]*
rater_age_groupgen z	0.51 [-0.71; 1.73]
rater_gendernonbinary	-1.22 [-3.88; 1.44]
rater_genderwoman	-0.27 [-1.12; 0.58]
cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	1.80 [0.24; 3.37]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.15 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.23 [0.80; 1.66]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.62; 1.45]*
rater_age_groupgen x+:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-1.54 [-2.89; -0.19]*
rater_age_groupgen z:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.62 [-2.54; 1.30]
rater_genderwoman:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	1.04 [-0.34; 2.43]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.12
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.63
AIC	12375.16
BIC	12542.71
Log Likelihood	-6165.58
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.06
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.55
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.95

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; cor_cultural_zone = English-Speaking; degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 71. DICES Expert: Demographics x Culture interaction (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * (cor_SurvSAgg) + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-1.13 [-2.59; 0.33]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	0.97 [-0.79; 2.73]
rater_ethnicityAsian/Asian subcontinent	-0.49 [-1.75; 0.78]
rater_ethnicityBlack/African American	0.63 [-0.61; 1.87]
rater_ethnicityLatinX, Latino, Hispanic or Spanish Origin	0.20 [-0.91; 1.31]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern or North African	1.50 [-0.39; 3.39]
rater_ethnicityMixed	2.26 [-1.25; 5.76]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander	3.31 [0.76; 5.85]*
rater_age_groupgen x+	0.19 [-0.88; 1.26]
rater_age_groupgen z	-0.03 [-1.33; 1.27]
rater_gendernonbinary	-1.22 [-3.88; 1.44]
rater_genderwoman	0.64 [-0.32; 1.60]
cor_SurvSAgg	-1.11 [-2.07; -0.15]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.15 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.23 [0.80; 1.66]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.62; 1.45]*
rater_age_groupgen x+:cor_SurvSAgg	0.95 [0.11; 1.78]*
rater_age_groupgen z:cor_SurvSAgg	0.38 [-0.80; 1.57]
rater_genderwoman:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.64 [-1.50; 0.21]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.12
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.63
AIC	12375.16
BIC	12542.71
Log Likelihood	-6165.58
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.06
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.55
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	2.95

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 72. DICES Expert: Demographics x selected culture-values interaction (surv) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ cor_quadrant + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-2.07 [-2.60; -1.55]*
cor_quadrantIII	1.05 [0.35; 1.75]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.14 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.22 [0.79; 1.65]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.61; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.06
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.62
AIC	12387.38
BIC	12448.30
Log Likelihood	-6185.69
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.05
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.54
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.30

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cor_quadrant = I; degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 73. DICES Expert: Culture quadrants (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cor_quadrant + degree_of_harm + (1 harm_type/item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	-2.80 [-3.67; -1.94]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	0.98 [-0.82; 2.77]
rater_ethnicityAsian/Asian subcontinent	-0.56 [-1.85; 0.73]
rater_ethnicityBlack/African American	0.66 [-0.60; 1.93]
rater_ethnicityLatinX, Latino, Hispanic or Spanish Origin	0.09 [-1.05; 1.22]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern or North African	1.59 [-0.33; 3.52]
rater_ethnicityMixed	1.91 [-1.67; 5.48]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander	2.96 [0.37; 5.55]*
rater_age_groupgen x+	1.25 [0.74; 1.77]*
rater_age_groupgen z	0.29 [-0.65; 1.23]
rater_gendernonbinary	-0.95 [-3.64; 1.74]
rater_genderwoman	0.18 [-0.50; 0.86]
cor_quadrantIII	1.80 [0.56; 3.03]*
degree_of_harmDebatable	1.15 [0.72; 1.57]*
degree_of_harmExtreme	1.23 [0.80; 1.66]*
degree_of_harmModerate	1.03 [0.62; 1.45]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.11
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.63
AIC	12376.62
BIC	12521.32
Log Likelihood	-6169.31
Num. obs.	15000
Num. groups: item_id:harm_type	306
Num. groups: harm_type	123
Num. groups: rater_id	119
Var: item_id:harm_type (Intercept)	1.06
Var: harm_type (Intercept)	0.55
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	3.09

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; cor_quadrant = I; degree_of_harm = Benign.

Table 74. DICES Expert: Demographics + Quadrants additive (GLMER, binomial)

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	harmful ~ (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.95 [0.84; 1.07]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84661.99
BIC	84703.30
Log Likelihood	-42325.99
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.36
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 75. DIVE: Null model (LMM)

Table 84. DIVE: Demographics x Culture interaction (LMM)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * cob_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.68 [0.48; 0.88]*
rater_ethnicityblack	0.42 [0.20; 0.64]*
rater_ethnicitylatinx	0.06 [-0.12; 0.25]
rater_ethnicitysouthasian	0.27 [0.06; 0.47]*
rater_ethnicitywhite	-0.02 [-0.20; 0.16]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.02 [-0.16; 0.13]
rater_age_groupgenz	-0.03 [-0.17; 0.11]
rater_genderwoman	0.26 [0.15; 0.38]*
cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.62 [0.12; 1.12]*
cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	-0.84 [-2.67; 1.00]
cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.13 [-0.28; 0.53]
cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.27 [-0.72; 1.26]
cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	-0.27 [-2.27; 1.74]
cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	1.11 [-0.06; 2.27]
cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.01 [-0.59; 0.58]
rater_ethnicityblack:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.53 [-1.03; -0.03]*
rater_ethnicitysouthasian:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.28 [-0.83; 0.28]
rater_ethnicitylatinx:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	1.41 [-0.02; 2.84]
rater_ethnicitysouthasian:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.11 [-0.67; 0.89]
rater_ethnicityblack:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	-1.33 [-2.70; 0.03]
rater_ethnicitylatinx:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.24 [-1.02; 0.53]
rater_ethnicitysouthasian:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.95 [-1.77; -0.14]*
rater_ethnicitywhite:cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	-0.18 [-1.82; 1.47]
rater_ethnicitylatinx:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-1.20 [-2.85; 0.45]
rater_ethnicitywhite:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-1.75 [-3.39; -0.10]*
rater_ethnicitysouthasian:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.07 [-0.66; 0.51]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.13 [-0.52; 0.25]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.01 [-0.35; 0.33]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.42 [-1.22; 2.07]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	-0.01 [-0.47; 0.45]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	-0.17 [-0.68; 0.34]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.06 [-0.44; 0.57]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.59 [-0.01; 1.20]

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DIVE (continued)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * cob_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	0.14 [-1.50; 1.78]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.18 [-0.32; 0.68]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.33 [-0.28; 0.94]
rater_genderwoman:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.13 [-0.43; 0.16]
rater_genderwoman:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.08 [-0.34; 0.49]
rater_genderwoman:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.11 [-0.36; 0.58]
rater_genderwoman:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.05 [-0.49; 0.38]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.04
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	84687.04
BIC	85050.58
Log Likelihood	-42299.52
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.32
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = eastasian; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; cob_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.78 [0.61; 0.95]*
rater_ethnicityblack	0.31 [0.15; 0.47]*
rater_ethnicitylatinx	0.01 [-0.14; 0.16]
rater_ethnicitysouthasian	0.15 [-0.00; 0.30]
rater_ethnicitywhite	-0.14 [-0.29; 0.01]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.02 [-0.14; 0.10]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.01 [-0.11; 0.12]
rater_genderwoman	0.25 [0.15; 0.34]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84643.34
BIC	84742.49
Log Likelihood	-42309.67
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.33
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = eastasian; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man.

Table 76. DIVE: Demographics model (LMM)

	harmful ~ cob_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.90 [0.78; 1.01]*
cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.33 [0.18; 0.48]*
cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.23 [-0.38; 0.83]
cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.03 [-0.17; 0.23]
cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.09 [-0.12; 0.31]
cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	-0.37 [-1.06; 0.33]
cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.18 [-0.52; 0.87]
cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.15 [-0.07; 0.37]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84666.69
BIC	84765.83
Log Likelihood	-42321.34
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.35
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cob_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 77. DIVE: Culture model (LMM)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ cob_TrAdAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.97 [0.85; 1.08]*
cob_TrAdAgg	-0.11 [-0.17; -0.05]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84657.31
BIC	84706.88
Log Likelihood	-42322.65
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.36
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 78. DIVE: Culture values (TradAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ cob_SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.04 [0.91; 1.16]*
cob_SurvSAgg	-0.08 [-0.13; -0.04]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84657.52
BIC	84707.09
Log Likelihood	-42322.76
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.36
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 79. DIVE: Culture values (SurvSAgg) (LMM)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ cob_TrAdAgg + cob_SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	1.01 [0.88; 1.14]*
cob_TrAdAgg	-0.06 [-0.15; 0.03]
cob_SurvSAgg	-0.05 [-0.12; 0.02]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84662.22
BIC	84720.05
Log Likelihood	-42324.11
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.36
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 80. DIVE: Culture values (TradAgg + SurvSAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ cob_TrAdAgg * cob_SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.97 [0.84; 1.11]*
cob_TrAdAgg	-0.06 [-0.15; 0.03]
cob_SurvSAgg	-0.07 [-0.14; 0.00]
cob_TrAdAgg:cob_SurvSAgg	0.07 [0.02; 0.13]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84663.23
BIC	84729.33
Log Likelihood	-42323.62
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.35
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 81. DIVE: Culture values (TradAgg * SurvSAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cob_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.75 [0.56; 0.93]*
rater_ethnicityblack	0.25 [0.06; 0.43]*
rater_ethnicitylatinx	0.04 [-0.13; 0.20]
rater_ethnicitysouthasian	0.14 [-0.03; 0.31]
rater_ethnicitywhite	-0.11 [-0.27; 0.06]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.01 [-0.13; 0.11]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.01 [-0.11; 0.13]
rater_genderwoman	0.25 [0.15; 0.35]*
cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.18 [0.01; 0.35]*
cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.15 [-0.44; 0.75]
cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.06 [-0.16; 0.28]
cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.01 [-0.22; 0.21]
cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	-0.32 [-1.00; 0.36]
cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	0.11 [-0.57; 0.79]
cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.05 [-0.18; 0.29]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84663.47
BIC	84820.45
Log Likelihood	-42312.74
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.33
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = eastasian; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; cob_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 82. DIVE: Demographics + Culture additive (LMM)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cob_TradAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.79 [0.62; 0.97]*
rater_ethnicityblack	0.28 [0.11; 0.45]*
rater_ethnicitylatinx	-0.00 [-0.15; 0.15]
rater_ethnicitysouthasian	0.13 [-0.02; 0.29]
rater_ethnicitywhite	-0.14 [-0.28; 0.01]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.02 [-0.14; 0.10]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.01 [-0.11; 0.12]
rater_genderwoman	0.24 [0.15; 0.34]*
cob_TradAgg	-0.03 [-0.10; 0.04]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84649.44
BIC	84756.85
Log Likelihood	-42311.72
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.33
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = eastasian; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man.

Table 83. DIVE: Demographics + selected culture-values additive (trad) (LMM)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * (cob_TrAdAgg) + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.84 [0.66; 1.03]*
rater_ethnicityblack	0.27 [0.09; 0.45]*
rater_ethnicitylatinx	-0.03 [-0.19; 0.12]
rater_ethnicitysouthasian	0.10 [-0.06; 0.26]
rater_ethnicitywhite	-0.12 [-0.33; 0.08]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.03 [-0.15; 0.09]
rater_age_groupgenz	-0.00 [-0.12; 0.12]
rater_genderwoman	0.24 [0.14; 0.34]*
cob_TrAdAgg	-0.15 [-0.33; 0.04]
rater_ethnicityblack:cob_TrAdAgg	0.18 [-0.03; 0.38]
rater_ethnicitylatinx:cob_TrAdAgg	-0.01 [-0.29; 0.27]
rater_ethnicitysouthasian:cob_TrAdAgg	0.20 [0.01; 0.39]*
rater_ethnicitywhite:cob_TrAdAgg	0.01 [-0.27; 0.29]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_TrAdAgg	-0.01 [-0.16; 0.14]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_TrAdAgg	-0.09 [-0.24; 0.06]
rater_genderwoman:cob_TrAdAgg	0.06 [-0.06; 0.18]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84675.82
BIC	84841.06
Log Likelihood	-42317.91
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.33
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = eastasian; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man.

Table 85. DIVE: Demographics x selected culture-values interaction (trad) (LMM)

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	harmful ~ cob_quadrant + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.90 [0.78; 1.02]*
cob_quadrantII	0.03 [-0.16; 0.21]
cob_quadrantIII	0.27 [0.14; 0.39]*
cob_quadrantIV	0.00 [-0.23; 0.23]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84660.27
BIC	84726.37
Log Likelihood	-42322.13
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.35
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cob_quadrant = I.

Table 86. DIVE: Culture quadrants (LMM)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cob_quadrant + (1 rater_id) + (1 topic/item_id)
(Intercept)	0.75 [0.57; 0.94]*
rater_ethnicityblack	0.27 [0.09; 0.44]*
rater_ethnicitylatinx	0.03 [-0.13; 0.19]
rater_ethnicitysouthasian	0.14 [-0.02; 0.30]
rater_ethnicitywhite	-0.12 [-0.28; 0.04]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.01 [-0.13; 0.11]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.00 [-0.11; 0.12]
rater_genderwoman	0.25 [0.16; 0.35]*
cob_quadrantII	0.04 [-0.16; 0.24]
cob_quadrantIII	0.13 [-0.01; 0.27]
cob_quadrantIV	-0.11 [-0.34; 0.12]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	84652.95
BIC	84776.88
Log Likelihood	-42311.47
Num. obs.	28632
Num. groups: item_id:topic	1000
Num. groups: rater_id	593
Num. groups: topic	19
Var: item_id:topic (Intercept)	0.33
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.33
Var: topic (Intercept)	0.05
Var: Residual	0.97

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = eastasian; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; cob_quadrant = I.

Table 87. DIVE: Demographics + Quadrants additive (LMM)

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	harmful ~ (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	3.04 [2.94; 3.15]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.46
AIC	130389.21
BIC	130424.39
Log Likelihood	-65190.60
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.49
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 88. Severity: Null model (LMM)

Table 97. Severity: Demographics x Culture interaction (LMM)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * cor_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.52 [2.26; 2.79]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	0.31 [-0.19; 0.82]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native,White	0.57 [-0.40; 1.54]
rater_ethnicityAsian	-0.22 [-0.76; 0.33]
rater_ethnicityAsian,White	-0.11 [-1.23; 1.02]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American	-0.06 [-0.38; 0.26]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	0.33 [-1.06; 1.72]
rater_age_group18 - 24	0.20 [-0.17; 0.57]
rater_age_group35 - 44	-0.08 [-0.35; 0.20]
rater_age_group45 - 54	0.21 [-0.10; 0.52]
rater_age_group55 - 64	0.42 [-0.04; 0.88]
rater_age_group65 - 74	0.46 [0.12; 0.80]*
rater_age_group75 - 84	0.22 [-0.49; 0.94]
rater_age_group85 or older	0.71 [-0.68; 2.09]
rater_gendernonbinary	-0.49 [-1.12; 0.13]
rater_genderWoman	0.12 [-0.09; 0.33]
cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.43 [0.14; 0.72]*
cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.51 [0.22; 0.81]*
cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.54 [-0.08; 1.16]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.05 [-1.51; 1.42]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.17 [-0.40; 0.73]
rater_ethnicityAsian,White:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.35 [-0.93; 1.64]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.46 [-1.11; 0.19]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.18 [-1.88; 1.52]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.06 [-0.80; 0.92]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.39 [-0.18; 0.95]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.21 [-0.22; 0.64]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.21 [-1.81; 1.39]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.93 [-1.81; -0.05]*
rater_ethnicityAsian:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.23 [-0.56; 1.01]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.58 [-2.10; 0.94]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.65 [-1.38; 2.68]
rater_age_group18 - 24:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.18 [-0.62; 0.25]
rater_age_group35 - 44:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.13 [-0.21; 0.47]
rater_age_group45 - 54:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.07 [-0.43; 0.28]

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Severity (continued)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * cor_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
rater_age_group55 - 64:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.18 [-0.71; 0.34]
rater_age_group65 - 74:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.36 [-1.08; 0.35]
rater_age_group75 - 84:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.19 [-1.87; 2.26]
rater_age_group85 or older:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.42 [-1.53; 2.37]
rater_age_group18 - 24:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.48 [-0.92; -0.04]*
rater_age_group35 - 44:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.06 [-0.28; 0.40]
rater_age_group45 - 54:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.24 [-0.61; 0.13]
rater_age_group55 - 64:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.40 [-0.94; 0.14]
rater_age_group65 - 74:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.52 [-1.55; 0.52]
rater_age_group18 - 24:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.46 [-0.92; -0.00]*
rater_age_group35 - 44:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.00 [-0.34; 0.35]
rater_age_group45 - 54:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.24 [-0.60; 0.12]
rater_age_group55 - 64:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.68 [-1.21; -0.15]*
rater_age_group65 - 74:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.69 [-1.47; 0.08]
rater_gendernonbinary:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-0.06 [-1.21; 1.10]
rater_genderWoman:cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.07 [-0.18; 0.32]
rater_gendernonbinary:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.89 [-0.13; 1.91]
rater_genderWoman:cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	-0.04 [-0.29; 0.22]
rater_genderWoman:cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.02 [-0.24; 0.28]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.03
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.47
AIC	130440.79
BIC	130942.20
Log Likelihood	-65163.39
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.46
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = 25 - 34; rater_gender = Man; cor_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 98. Severity: Demographics x selected culture-values interaction (inter) (LMM)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * (cor_TradAgg * cor_SurvSAgg) + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.96 [2.74; 3.18]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	-0.50 [-1.24; 0.23]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native,White	0.55 [-0.42; 1.52]
rater_ethnicityAsian	0.08 [-0.12; 0.28]
rater_ethnicityAsian,White	0.52 [-1.37; 2.41]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American	1.90 [-1.09; 4.89]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	-0.59 [-2.32; 1.15]
rater_age_group18 - 24	-0.30 [-0.57; -0.04]*
rater_age_group35 - 44	-0.14 [-0.34; 0.05]
rater_age_group45 - 54	-0.00 [-0.20; 0.19]
rater_age_group55 - 64	-0.12 [-0.41; 0.17]
rater_age_group65 - 74	-0.12 [-0.90; 0.66]
rater_age_group75 - 84	0.22 [-0.45; 0.89]
rater_age_group85 or older	0.77 [-0.33; 1.88]
rater_gendernonbinary	-0.23 [-1.41; 0.96]
rater_genderWoman	0.08 [-0.07; 0.23]
cor_TradAgg	-0.13 [-0.64; 0.38]
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.26 [-0.47; -0.05]*
cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.36 [-0.60; -0.12]*

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Severity (continued)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * (cor_TradAgg * cor_SurvSAgg) + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native:cor_TradAgg	-0.55 [-1.98; 0.88]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cor_TradAgg	0.05 [-0.46; 0.55]
rater_ethnicityAsian,White:cor_TradAgg	1.09 [-2.61; 4.78]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American:cor_TradAgg	6.37 [-4.70; 17.44]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander:cor_TradAgg	-2.76 [-7.32; 1.80]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native:cor_SurvSAgg	0.53 [-0.11; 1.16]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.08 [-0.34; 0.19]
rater_ethnicityAsian,White:cor_SurvSAgg	0.83 [-2.18; 3.85]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American:cor_SurvSAgg	-1.93 [-5.10; 1.25]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander:cor_SurvSAgg	0.86 [-0.77; 2.49]
rater_age_group18 - 24:cor_TradAgg	-0.09 [-0.41; 0.23]
rater_age_group35 - 44:cor_TradAgg	-0.08 [-0.34; 0.17]
rater_age_group45 - 54:cor_TradAgg	-0.00 [-0.24; 0.23]
rater_age_group55 - 64:cor_TradAgg	-0.07 [-0.40; 0.26]
rater_age_group65 - 74:cor_TradAgg	-0.02 [-0.94; 0.90]
rater_age_group75 - 84:cor_TradAgg	0.06 [-1.40; 1.53]
rater_age_group85 or older:cor_TradAgg	-0.49 [-3.79; 2.80]
rater_age_group18 - 24:cor_SurvSAgg	0.29 [0.03; 0.56]*
rater_age_group35 - 44:cor_SurvSAgg	0.06 [-0.14; 0.25]
rater_age_group45 - 54:cor_SurvSAgg	0.14 [-0.06; 0.34]
rater_age_group55 - 64:cor_SurvSAgg	0.24 [-0.07; 0.54]
rater_age_group65 - 74:cor_SurvSAgg	0.34 [-0.23; 0.91]
rater_gendernonbinary:cor_TradAgg	-0.32 [-1.50; 0.86]
rater_genderWoman:cor_TradAgg	-0.05 [-0.22; 0.13]
rater_gendernonbinary:cor_SurvSAgg	-1.27 [-3.94; 1.40]
rater_genderWoman:cor_SurvSAgg	0.03 [-0.11; 0.18]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.73 [-0.26; 1.73]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.20 [-0.48; 0.07]
rater_ethnicityAsian,White:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	1.61 [-3.08; 6.30]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.88 [-1.60; -0.16]*
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.20 [-1.29; 1.68]
rater_age_group18 - 24:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.50 [0.15; 0.86]*
rater_age_group35 - 44:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.27 [-0.02; 0.56]
rater_age_group45 - 54:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.25 [-0.03; 0.53]
rater_age_group55 - 64:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.54 [0.12; 0.96]*
rater_age_group65 - 74:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.51 [-0.40; 1.43]
rater_gendernonbinary:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	-1.85 [-5.17; 1.46]
rater_genderWoman:cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	0.13 [-0.07; 0.34]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.03
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.47
AIC	130458.20
BIC	130986.01
Log Likelihood	-65169.10
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.47
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = 25 - 34; rater_gender = Man.

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	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.92 [2.79; 3.06]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	-0.07 [-0.37; 0.23]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native,White	0.68 [-0.31; 1.67]
rater_ethnicityAsian	0.12 [0.04; 0.20]*
rater_ethnicityAsian,White	0.25 [-0.28; 0.78]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American	-0.08 [-0.28; 0.11]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	0.28 [-0.25; 0.81]
rater_age_group18 - 24	-0.13 [-0.26; -0.00]*
rater_age_group35 - 44	-0.04 [-0.15; 0.06]
rater_age_group45 - 54	0.04 [-0.06; 0.14]
rater_age_group55 - 64	0.05 [-0.10; 0.19]
rater_age_group65 - 74	0.04 [-0.21; 0.28]
rater_age_group75 - 84	0.03 [-0.60; 0.66]
rater_age_group85 or older	0.73 [-0.26; 1.72]
rater_gendernonbinary	-0.18 [-0.63; 0.26]
rater_genderWoman	0.12 [0.05; 0.20]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.47
AIC	130416.69
BIC	130583.83
Log Likelihood	-65189.35
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.48
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = 25 - 34; rater_gender = Man.

Table 89. Severity: Demographics model (LMM)

	harmful ~ cor_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.73 [2.59; 2.87]*
cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.36 [0.24; 0.48]*
cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.42 [0.30; 0.54]*
cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.31 [0.19; 0.44]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.46
AIC	130360.15
BIC	130421.72
Log Likelihood	-65173.07
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.48
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cor_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 90. Severity: Culture model (LMM)

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	harmful ~ TradAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.90 [2.79; 3.02]*
cor_TradAgg	-0.23 [-0.30; -0.15]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.46
AIC	130360.20
BIC	130404.19
Log Likelihood	-65175.10
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.48
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 91. Severity: Culture values (TradAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	3.03 [2.93; 3.14]*
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.11 [-0.15; -0.07]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.46
AIC	130371.45
BIC	130415.43
Log Likelihood	-65180.72
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.48
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 92. Severity: Culture values (SurvSAgg) (LMM)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ TradAgg + SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.93 [2.81; 3.05]*
cor_TradAgg	-0.17 [-0.26; -0.09]*
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.06 [-0.11; -0.01]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.46
AIC	130362.10
BIC	130414.88
Log Likelihood	-65175.05
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.48
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 93. Severity: Culture values (TradAgg + SurvSAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ TradAgg * SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.99 [2.87; 3.11]*
cor_TradAgg	-0.14 [-0.23; -0.05]*
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.15 [-0.22; -0.08]*
cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.17 [-0.27; -0.07]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.46
AIC	130357.20
BIC	130418.77
Log Likelihood	-65171.60
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.47
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 94. Severity: Culture values (TradAgg * SurvSAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cor_cult_cluster + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.61 [2.44; 2.77]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	-0.03 [-0.32; 0.27]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native,White	0.60 [-0.38; 1.57]
rater_ethnicityAsian	0.05 [-0.05; 0.14]
rater_ethnicityAsian,White	0.18 [-0.34; 0.71]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American	-0.04 [-0.24; 0.15]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	0.23 [-0.29; 0.76]
rater_age_group18 - 24	-0.13 [-0.26; 0.00]
rater_age_group35 - 44	-0.02 [-0.13; 0.08]
rater_age_group45 - 54	0.06 [-0.04; 0.15]
rater_age_group55 - 64	0.06 [-0.09; 0.20]
rater_age_group65 - 74	0.24 [-0.00; 0.49]
rater_age_group75 - 84	0.25 [-0.38; 0.87]
rater_age_group85 or older	0.85 [-0.13; 1.82]
rater_gendernonbinary	-0.19 [-0.63; 0.25]
rater_genderWoman	0.15 [0.07; 0.22]*
cor_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.38 [0.25; 0.52]*
cor_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.45 [0.31; 0.58]*
cor_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.33 [0.17; 0.48]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.47
AIC	130388.34
BIC	130581.87
Log Likelihood	-65172.17
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.47
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = 25 - 34; rater_gender = Man; cor_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 95. Severity: Demographics + Culture additive (LMM)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cor_TradAgg * cor_SurvSAgg + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.92 [2.78; 3.06]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	-0.05 [-0.35; 0.24]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native,White	0.55 [-0.42; 1.53]
rater_ethnicityAsian	0.01 [-0.09; 0.12]
rater_ethnicityAsian,White	0.15 [-0.37; 0.68]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American	-0.02 [-0.21; 0.18]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	0.25 [-0.27; 0.78]
rater_age_group18 - 24	-0.12 [-0.25; 0.01]
rater_age_group35 - 44	-0.03 [-0.13; 0.07]
rater_age_group45 - 54	0.04 [-0.05; 0.14]
rater_age_group55 - 64	0.05 [-0.10; 0.19]
rater_age_group65 - 74	0.23 [-0.02; 0.48]
rater_age_group75 - 84	0.24 [-0.39; 0.86]
rater_age_group85 or older	0.82 [-0.16; 1.79]
rater_gendernonbinary	-0.17 [-0.61; 0.27]
rater_genderWoman	0.15 [0.07; 0.22]*
cor_TradAgg	-0.13 [-0.24; -0.02]*
cor_SurvSAgg	-0.17 [-0.25; -0.10]*
cor_TradAgg:cor_SurvSAgg	-0.19 [-0.29; -0.09]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.47
AIC	130389.03
BIC	130582.55
Log Likelihood	-65172.51
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.47
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = 25 - 34; rater_gender = Man.

Table 96. Severity: Demographics + selected culture-values additive (inter) (LMM)

	harmful ~ cor_quadrant + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.73 [2.59; 2.87]*
cor_quadrantIII	0.35 [0.24; 0.46]*
cor_quadrantIV	0.39 [0.27; 0.52]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.46
AIC	130357.10
BIC	130409.88
Log Likelihood	-65172.55
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.48
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cor_quadrant = I.

Table 99. Severity: Culture quadrants (LMM)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cor_quadrant + (1 rater_id) + (1 item_id)
(Intercept)	2.60 [2.44; 2.77]*
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native	-0.06 [-0.35; 0.24]
rater_ethnicityAmerican Indian or Alaska Native,White	0.57 [-0.40; 1.55]
rater_ethnicityAsian	-0.01 [-0.10; 0.09]
rater_ethnicityAsian,White	0.13 [-0.39; 0.66]
rater_ethnicityBlack or African American	-0.03 [-0.22; 0.17]
rater_ethnicityNative Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	0.23 [-0.30; 0.75]
rater_age_group18 - 24	-0.12 [-0.25; 0.01]
rater_age_group35 - 44	-0.02 [-0.13; 0.08]
rater_age_group45 - 54	0.06 [-0.04; 0.16]
rater_age_group55 - 64	0.06 [-0.09; 0.20]
rater_age_group65 - 74	0.24 [-0.00; 0.49]
rater_age_group75 - 84	0.25 [-0.38; 0.87]
rater_age_group85 or older	0.84 [-0.14; 1.81]
rater_gendernonbinary	-0.21 [-0.65; 0.23]
rater_genderWoman	0.15 [0.08; 0.23]*
cor_quadrantIII	0.41 [0.28; 0.53]*
cor_quadrantIV	0.45 [0.30; 0.60]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.47
AIC	130386.51
BIC	130571.24
Log Likelihood	-65172.25
Num. obs.	48860
Num. groups: rater_id	1416
Num. groups: item_id	66
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.47
Var: item_id (Intercept)	0.17
Var: Residual	0.77

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = 25 - 34; rater_gender = Man; cor_quadrant = I.

Table 100. Severity: Demographics + Quadrants additive (LMM)

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	harmful ~ (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.41 [0.10; 0.72]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5273.38
BIC	5293.38
Log Likelihood	-2633.69
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.84
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.24

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 101. NLPositionality: Null model (GLMER, binomial)

Table 110. NLPositionality: Demographics x Culture interaction (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * CoLR_Cultural_Cluster + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.34 [-0.08; 0.77]
rater_ethnicityArab	-4.14 [-7.18; -1.10]*
rater_ethnicityasian, asian american	0.07 [-0.24; 0.37]
rater_ethnicityblack, african american	0.00 [-0.38; 0.39]
rater_ethnicityGreek	2.50 [-0.05; 5.05]
rater_ethnicityJewish	-0.52 [-2.57; 1.53]
rater_ethnicitylatino/latina, hispanic	0.10 [-0.23; 0.42]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern	0.67 [-1.52; 2.86]
rater_ethnicitynative american, american indian, alaska native	0.82 [0.03; 1.61]*
rater_ethnicitypacific islander, native australian	0.19 [-0.85; 1.22]
rater_age_groupboomer	-0.57 [-1.33; 0.20]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.32 [-0.83; 0.18]
rater_age_groupgenz	-0.08 [-0.39; 0.23]
rater_gendernon-binary	-0.01 [-0.37; 0.35]
rater_genderwoman	0.28 [0.03; 0.52]*
colr_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.11 [-1.43; 1.66]
colr_cultural_zoneConfucian	-1.19 [-2.83; 0.45]
colr_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.25 [-2.21; 2.71]
colr_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-1.02 [-3.40; 1.35]
colr_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	14.33 [-76.04; 104.70]
rater_ethnicityasian, asian american:colr_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	2.85 [-1.23; 6.92]
rater_ethnicityasian, asian american:colr_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.79 [-2.95; 4.54]
rater_age_groupgenz:colr_cultural_zoneConfucian	0.89 [-1.22; 3.01]
rater_age_groupgenx:colr_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-13.03 [-103.41; 77.35]
rater_age_groupgenz:colr_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-14.94 [-105.30; 75.41]
rater_genderwoman:colr_cultural_zoneConfucian	-1.55 [-3.67; 0.56]
rater_genderwoman:colr_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.27 [-1.77; 2.30]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.05
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.70
AIC	5285.56
BIC	5478.86
Log Likelihood	-2613.78
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.71

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NLPositionality (continued)

harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) *
CoLR_Cultural_Cluster +
(1 | item_id) + (1 | rater_id)

Var: item_id (Intercept)

6.23

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = white; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; colr_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.36 [-0.05; 0.78]
rater_ethnicityArab	-4.12 [-7.17; -1.07]*
rater_ethnicityasian, asian american	0.03 [-0.26; 0.31]
rater_ethnicityblack, african american	0.02 [-0.35; 0.40]
rater_ethnicityGreek	2.48 [-0.10; 5.06]
rater_ethnicityJewish	-0.52 [-2.57; 1.54]
rater_ethnicitylatino/latina, hispanic	0.11 [-0.21; 0.44]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern	0.71 [-1.51; 2.93]
rater_ethnicitynative american, american indian, alaska native	0.82 [0.03; 1.62]*
rater_ethnicitypacific islander, native australian	0.18 [-0.86; 1.22]
rater_age_groupboomer	-0.56 [-1.33; 0.21]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.23 [-0.72; 0.27]
rater_age_groupgenz	-0.10 [-0.40; 0.20]
rater_gendernon-binary	-0.01 [-0.38; 0.35]
rater_genderwoman	0.24 [0.00; 0.48]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5278.88
BIC	5392.19
Log Likelihood	-2622.44
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.75
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.20

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = white; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man.

Table 102. NLPositionality: Demographics model (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ CoLR_Cultural_Cluster + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.42 [0.11; 0.73]*
colr_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.48 [-0.90; 1.87]
colr_cultural_zoneConfucian	-1.00 [-1.93; -0.08]*
colr_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.60 [-1.30; 2.50]
colr_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-0.82 [-3.27; 1.62]
colr_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.02 [-0.90; 0.94]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5277.75
BIC	5331.07
Log Likelihood	-2630.87
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.82
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.26

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: colr_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 103. NLPositionality: Culture model (GLMER, binomial)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ TradAgg + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.49 [0.17; 0.80]*
colr_TradAgg	-0.55 [-1.06; -0.03]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5271.19
BIC	5297.85
Log Likelihood	-2631.59
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.83
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.24

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 104. NLPositionality: Culture values (TradAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ SurvSAgg + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.31 [-0.23; 0.85]
colr_SurvSAgg	0.07 [-0.26; 0.40]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5275.22
BIC	5301.88
Log Likelihood	-2633.61
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.84
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.24

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 105. NLPositionality: Culture values (SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ TradAgg + SurvSAgg + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.19 [-0.36; 0.74]
colr_TradAgg	-0.68 [-1.23; -0.13]*
colr_SurvSAgg	0.23 [-0.12; 0.59]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5271.60
BIC	5304.93
Log Likelihood	-2630.80
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.82
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.26

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 106. NLPositionality: Culture values (TradAgg + SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ TradAgg * SurvSAgg + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.19 [-0.36; 0.74]
colr_TradAgg	-0.69 [-1.24; -0.14]*
colr_SurvSAgg	0.22 [-0.14; 0.58]
colr_TradAgg:colr_SurvSAgg	0.10 [-0.38; 0.59]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5273.44
BIC	5313.43
Log Likelihood	-2630.72
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.82
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.26

* 0 outside the confidence interval.

Table 107. NLPositionality: Culture values (TradAgg * SurvSAgg) (GLMER, binomial)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + CoLR_Cultural_Cluster + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.36 [-0.06; 0.79]
rater_ethnicityArab	-4.13 [-7.17; -1.09]*
rater_ethnicityasian, asian american	0.09 [-0.21; 0.40]
rater_ethnicityblack, african american	-0.01 [-0.40; 0.37]
rater_ethnicityGreek	2.48 [-0.08; 5.05]
rater_ethnicityJewish	-0.53 [-2.58; 1.53]
rater_ethnicitylatino/latina, hispanic	0.10 [-0.23; 0.42]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern	0.70 [-1.51; 2.90]
rater_ethnicitynative american, american indian, alaska native	0.82 [0.03; 1.62]*
rater_ethnicitypacific islander, native australian	0.19 [-0.84; 1.23]
rater_age_groupboomer	-0.56 [-1.33; 0.20]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.25 [-0.75; 0.24]
rater_age_groupgenz	-0.09 [-0.40; 0.21]
rater_gendernon-binary	-0.02 [-0.38; 0.35]
rater_genderwoman	0.25 [0.00; 0.49]*
colr_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.57 [-0.84; 1.98]
colr_cultural_zoneConfucian	-1.04 [-1.98; -0.11]*
colr_cultural_zoneLatin America	0.57 [-1.32; 2.46]
colr_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-1.01 [-3.39; 1.38]
colr_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.01 [-0.93; 0.94]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5282.50
BIC	5429.14
Log Likelihood	-2619.25
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.73
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.22

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = white; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; colr_cultural_zone = English-Speaking.

Table 108. NLPositionality: Demographics + Culture additive (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + colr_TradAgg + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.42 [0.00; 0.84]*
rater_ethnicityArab	-4.12 [-7.16; -1.08]*
rater_ethnicityasian, asian american	0.03 [-0.25; 0.31]
rater_ethnicityblack, african american	-0.04 [-0.41; 0.34]
rater_ethnicityGreek	2.49 [-0.08; 5.06]
rater_ethnicityJewish	-0.51 [-2.56; 1.55]
rater_ethnicitylatino/latina, hispanic	0.09 [-0.23; 0.42]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern	0.68 [-1.53; 2.89]
rater_ethnicitynative american, american indian, alaska native	0.81 [0.02; 1.61]*
rater_ethnicitypacific islander, native australian	0.18 [-0.86; 1.21]
rater_age_groupboomer	-0.54 [-1.31; 0.22]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.24 [-0.73; 0.26]
rater_age_groupgenz	-0.07 [-0.37; 0.23]
rater_gendernon-binary	0.00 [-0.36; 0.37]
rater_genderwoman	0.27 [0.03; 0.51]*
colr_TradAgg	-0.60 [-1.10; -0.09]*
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5275.82
BIC	5395.79
Log Likelihood	-2619.91
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.74
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.21

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = white; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man.

Table 109. NLPositionality: Demographics + selected culture-values additive (trad) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * (colr_TradAgg) + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.44 [-0.06; 0.94]
rater_ethnicityArab	-4.11 [-7.15; -1.08]*
rater_ethnicityasian, asian american	0.05 [-0.34; 0.45]
rater_ethnicityblack, african american	-0.05 [-0.52; 0.41]
rater_ethnicityGreek	2.49 [-0.07; 5.05]
rater_ethnicityJewish	-0.53 [-2.58; 1.53]
rater_ethnicitylatino/latina, hispanic	0.06 [-0.38; 0.50]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern	0.68 [-1.52; 2.88]
rater_ethnicitynative american, american indian, alaska native	0.82 [0.02; 1.61]*
rater_ethnicitypacific islander, native australian	0.17 [-0.86; 1.21]
rater_age_groupboomer	-0.58 [-1.35; 0.19]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.09 [-0.69; 0.51]
rater_age_groupgenz	-0.12 [-0.49; 0.25]
rater_gendernon-binary	-0.01 [-0.37; 0.36]
rater_genderwoman	0.28 [-0.06; 0.62]
colr_TradAgg	-0.50 [-2.25; 1.25]
rater_ethnicityasian, asian american:colr_TradAgg	-0.29 [-1.98; 1.40]
rater_ethnicityblack, african american:colr_TradAgg	0.41 [-1.65; 2.46]
rater_ethnicitylatino/latina, hispanic:colr_TradAgg	0.25 [-1.74; 2.24]
rater_age_groupgenx:colr_TradAgg	-1.68 [-4.50; 1.14]
rater_age_groupgenz:colr_TradAgg	0.10 [-1.20; 1.39]
rater_genderwoman:colr_TradAgg	-0.08 [-1.61; 1.45]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5284.47
BIC	5444.44
Log Likelihood	-2618.24
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.73
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.22

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = white; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man.

Table 111. NLPositionality: Demographics x selected culture-values interaction (trad) (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ colr_quadrant + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.42 [0.11; 0.73]*
colr_quadrantII	-1.00 [-1.92; -0.08]*
colr_quadrantIII	0.26 [-0.55; 1.08]
colr_quadrantIV	0.09 [-1.39; 1.57]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.00
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5274.57
BIC	5314.56
Log Likelihood	-2631.28
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.82
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.25

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: colr_quadrant = I.

Table 112. NLPositionality: Culture quadrants (GLMER, binomial)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + colr_quadrant + (1 item_id) + (1 rater_id)
(Intercept)	0.37 [-0.05; 0.79]
rater_ethnicityArab	-4.13 [-7.17; -1.08]*
rater_ethnicityasian, asian american	0.08 [-0.22; 0.38]
rater_ethnicityblack, african american	0.00 [-0.38; 0.38]
rater_ethnicityGreek	2.48 [-0.09; 5.05]
rater_ethnicityJewish	-0.53 [-2.58; 1.53]
rater_ethnicitylatino/latina, hispanic	0.11 [-0.21; 0.43]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern	0.71 [-1.50; 2.92]
rater_ethnicitynative american, american indian, alaska native	0.83 [0.03; 1.62]*
rater_ethnicitypacific islander, native australian	0.20 [-0.84; 1.23]
rater_age_groupboomer	-0.57 [-1.34; 0.20]
rater_age_groupgenx	-0.26 [-0.75; 0.24]
rater_age_groupgenz	-0.10 [-0.40; 0.20]
rater_gendernon-binary	-0.02 [-0.39; 0.35]
rater_genderwoman	0.24 [-0.00; 0.48]
colr_quadrantII	-1.03 [-1.97; -0.10]*
colr_quadrantIII	0.30 [-0.53; 1.14]
colr_quadrantIV	0.00 [-1.46; 1.46]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.01
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.68
AIC	5279.57
BIC	5412.88
Log Likelihood	-2619.79
Num. obs.	5799
Num. groups: rater_id	502
Num. groups: item_id	299
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	0.74
Var: item_id (Intercept)	6.22

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = white; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = man; colr_quadrant = I.

Table 113. NLPositionality: Demographics + Quadrants additive (GLMER, binomial)

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	harmful ~ conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	13.62 [10.09; 17.16]*
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.22; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.96 [1.11; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.51 [-4.00; 0.98]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.73 [-1.96; 3.42]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.42
AIC	59499.43
BIC	59561.13
Log Likelihood	-29740.71
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	139.69
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.08
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.70
Var: Residual	214.38

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 114. PRISM: Null model (LMM)

Table 121. PRISM: Demographics + Culture additive (LMM)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cob_cult_cluster + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	14.74 [10.88; 18.60]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	-0.53 [-4.09; 3.03]
rater_ethnicityBlack / African	-3.27 [-6.61; 0.07]
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino	0.12 [-3.42; 3.66]
rater_ethnicityIndigenous / First Peoples	-11.64 [-20.90; -2.38]*
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern / Arab	-2.20 [-9.92; 5.52]
rater_ethnicityMixed	-2.28 [-5.73; 1.16]
rater_age_groupboomer	-0.78 [-3.94; 2.37]
rater_age_groupgenx	1.25 [-0.63; 3.14]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.95 [-1.07; 2.96]
rater_genderFemale	-3.34 [-4.84; -1.83]*
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender	-4.53 [-10.94; 1.87]
cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	2.85 [-2.24; 7.95]
cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.36 [-2.14; 2.86]
cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	8.46 [2.05; 14.87]*
cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	4.67 [0.56; 8.78]*
cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	2.13 [-2.79; 7.05]
cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	4.31 [1.12; 7.49]*
cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	1.11 [-1.72; 3.94]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.22; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.98 [1.12; 2.83]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.80 [-4.32; 0.72]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	-0.05 [-2.89; 2.79]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.04
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	59425.28
BIC	59610.39

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PRISM (continued)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cob_cult_cluster + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
Log Likelihood	-29685.64
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	134.36
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.05
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.41
Var: Residual	214.39

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; cob_cultural_zone = English-Speaking; conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 123. PRISM: Demographics x Culture interaction (LMM)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * cob_cult_cluster + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	14.15 [10.18; 18.11]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	-0.05 [-4.60; 4.49]
rater_ethnicityBlack / African	-0.54 [-6.00; 4.92]
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino	-3.68 [-10.40; 3.03]
rater_ethnicityIndigenous / First Peoples	-11.38 [-21.12; -1.64]*
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern / Arab	-2.87 [-14.41; 8.66]
rater_ethnicityMixed	-1.01 [-5.40; 3.38]
rater_age_groupboomer	-0.93 [-4.36; 2.51]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.46 [-1.76; 2.68]
rater_age_groupgenz	1.86 [-1.44; 5.16]
rater_genderFemale	-1.52 [-3.49; 0.44]
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender	-6.90 [-15.16; 1.36]
cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	1.95 [-20.61; 24.51]
cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	1.86 [-2.29; 6.01]
cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	1.83 [-11.55; 15.22]
cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	8.47 [-1.14; 18.08]
cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	5.85 [-2.34; 14.04]
cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	5.86 [0.62; 11.11]*
cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	4.72 [-1.08; 10.52]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.22; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.98 [1.12; 2.83]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.93 [-4.48; 0.62]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	-0.27 [-3.15; 2.61]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.04 [-21.43; 21.52]
rater_ethnicityBlack / African:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-10.18 [-30.38; 10.02]
rater_ethnicityMixed:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	6.58 [-27.66; 40.81]
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	12.68 [-14.01; 39.37]
rater_ethnicityMixed:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	-0.49 [-12.63; 11.65]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	5.80 [-8.94; 20.53]
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	3.69 [-8.03; 15.42]
rater_ethnicityMixed:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	-6.77 [-21.90; 8.36]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	20.98 [-10.06; 52.01]
rater_ethnicityBlack / African:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	9.39 [-17.07; 35.85]
rater_ethnicityMixed:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	5.56 [-14.31; 25.43]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-10.33 [-20.02; -0.64]*
rater_ethnicityBlack / African:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-5.61 [-13.63; 2.41]
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	2.10 [-7.17; 11.36]
rater_ethnicityIndigenous / First Peoples:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-6.07 [-36.22; 24.08]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern / Arab:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-2.26 [-18.24; 13.71]
rater_ethnicityMixed:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-4.76 [-14.44; 4.93]

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PRISM (continued)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * cob_cult_cluster + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	3.96 [-14.50; 22.42]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	12.07 [0.36; 23.77]*
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	-6.60 [-21.22; 8.02]
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	-5.48 [-22.18; 11.22]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	-2.33 [-9.89; 5.22]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	-0.54 [-6.31; 5.24]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	2.44 [-14.50; 19.39]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	-1.46 [-14.58; 11.67]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	5.52 [-5.66; 16.70]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	-2.44 [-10.58; 5.70]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	-9.98 [-24.53; 4.56]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	0.45 [-11.14; 12.03]
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	2.05 [-11.94; 16.04]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	8.20 [-0.25; 16.65]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-7.38 [-16.05; 1.28]
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	17.81 [-8.47; 44.09]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.37 [-9.92; 9.17]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	0.86 [-4.55; 6.28]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.58 [-9.46; 10.61]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	-2.92 [-7.78; 1.94]
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender:cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	7.81 [-19.17; 34.79]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	7.53 [-5.95; 21.01]
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender:cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	2.36 [-27.19; 31.91]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	-7.99 [-14.72; -1.26]*
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	-5.42 [-15.11; 4.28]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	-6.76 [-13.79; 0.26]
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender:cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	5.94 [-12.07; 23.95]
rater_genderFemale:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-3.43 [-7.96; 1.11]
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender:cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-3.58 [-30.75; 23.60]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.06
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.44
AIC	59203.86
BIC	59704.33
Log Likelihood	-29528.93
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	132.33
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.02
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.15
Var: Residual	214.45

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; cob_cultural_zone = English-Speaking; conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 124. PRISM: Demographics x selected culture-values interaction (trad) (LMM)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * (cob_TradAgg) + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	15.40 [11.33; 19.47]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	1.81 [-1.42; 5.03]
rater_ethnicityBlack / African	-1.64 [-4.89; 1.60]
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino	1.58 [-1.62; 4.78]
rater_ethnicityIndigenous / First Peoples	-17.18 [-42.38; 8.03]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern / Arab	-3.07 [-12.40; 6.26]

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PRISM (continued)

	harmful ~ (ethnicity + age + gender) * (cob_TrAdAgg) + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
rater_ethnicityMixed	-1.29 [-5.08; 2.51]
rater_age_groupboomer	1.17 [-2.83; 5.17]
rater_age_groupgenx	1.72 [-0.44; 3.88]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.98 [-1.19; 3.14]
rater_genderFemale	-4.16 [-5.86; -2.47]*
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender	-7.55 [-16.68; 1.58]
cob_TrAdAgg	-0.23 [-2.84; 2.39]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.22; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.98 [1.12; 2.83]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.95 [-4.53; 0.62]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.08 [-2.81; 2.97]
rater_ethnicityAsian:cob_TrAdAgg	-0.37 [-3.82; 3.07]
rater_ethnicityBlack / African:cob_TrAdAgg	1.82 [-2.79; 6.44]
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino:cob_TrAdAgg	-3.33 [-7.76; 1.10]
rater_ethnicityIndigenous / First Peoples:cob_TrAdAgg	10.10 [-39.30; 59.49]
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern / Arab:cob_TrAdAgg	1.70 [-13.47; 16.87]
rater_ethnicityMixed:cob_TrAdAgg	-3.11 [-9.56; 3.34]
rater_age_groupboomer:cob_TrAdAgg	-4.71 [-10.32; 0.90]
rater_age_groupgenx:cob_TrAdAgg	-1.77 [-4.72; 1.18]
rater_age_groupgenz:cob_TrAdAgg	0.56 [-2.50; 3.63]
rater_genderFemale:cob_TrAdAgg	2.62 [0.29; 4.96]*
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender:cob_TrAdAgg	6.98 [-5.28; 19.24]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.04
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	59416.93
BIC	59636.31
Log Likelihood	-29676.47
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	135.79
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.04
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.59
Var: Residual	214.40

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	15.38 [11.58; 19.19]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	1.89 [-1.04; 4.82]
rater_ethnicityBlack / African	-2.71 [-5.37; -0.05]*
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino	1.89 [-0.80; 4.59]
rater_ethnicityIndigenous / First Peoples	-12.14 [-21.43; -2.86]*
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern / Arab	-2.28 [-9.88; 5.32]
rater_ethnicityMixed	-2.13 [-5.52; 1.25]
rater_age_groupboomer	-1.22 [-4.33; 1.89]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.88 [-0.95; 2.70]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.92 [-1.07; 2.91]
rater_genderFemale	-3.18 [-4.68; -1.68]*
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender	-3.99 [-10.39; 2.42]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.07 [5.21; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.97 [1.11; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.81 [-4.34; 0.72]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.08 [-2.76; 2.92]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.03
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	59451.35
BIC	59588.47
Log Likelihood	-29705.68
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	135.87
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.05
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.54
Var: Residual	214.38

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 115. PRISM: Demographics model (LMM)

	harmful ~ cob_cult_cluster + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	13.01 [9.47; 16.55]*
cob_cultural_zoneAfrican-Islamic	0.84 [-3.74; 5.43]
cob_cultural_zoneCatholic Europe	0.40 [-1.97; 2.78]
cob_cultural_zoneConfucian	7.19 [1.68; 12.69]*
cob_cultural_zoneLatin America	4.63 [1.30; 7.97]*
cob_cultural_zoneOrthodox Europe	2.27 [-2.64; 7.18]
cob_cultural_zoneProtestant Europe	4.68 [1.52; 7.85]*
cob_cultural_zoneWest & South Asia	-0.16 [-2.40; 2.08]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.22; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.97 [1.11; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.64 [-4.13; 0.85]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.45 [-2.28; 3.19]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.03
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.42
AIC	59471.26
BIC	59580.95
Log Likelihood	-29719.63
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	137.70
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.08
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.60
Var: Residual	214.38

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cob_cultural_zone = English-Speaking; conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 116. PRISM: Culture model (LMM)

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	harmful ~ cob_TrAdAgg + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	13.47 [9.86; 17.07]*
cob_TrAdAgg	0.27 [-0.91; 1.45]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.21; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.96 [1.11; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.45 [-3.95; 1.05]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.84 [-1.89; 3.58]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.42
AIC	59500.40
BIC	59568.96
Log Likelihood	-29740.20
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	139.80
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.08
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.71
Var: Residual	214.38

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 117. PRISM: Culture values (TradAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ cob_SurvSAgg + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	13.40 [9.63; 17.17]*
cob_SurvSAgg	0.13 [-0.61; 0.86]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.22; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.97 [1.11; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.46 [-3.97; 1.04]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.83 [-1.92; 3.57]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.42
AIC	59501.44
BIC	59570.00
Log Likelihood	-29740.72
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	139.81
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.08
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.70
Var: Residual	214.38

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 118. PRISM: Culture values (SurvSAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ cob_TradAgg + cob_SurvSAgg + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	13.43 [9.66; 17.21]*
cob_TradAgg	0.24 [-1.31; 1.79]
cob_SurvSAgg	0.03 [-0.94; 0.99]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.21; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.96 [1.11; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.44 [-3.95; 1.06]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.85 [-1.90; 3.61]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.42
AIC	59501.98
BIC	59577.39
Log Likelihood	-29739.99
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	139.94
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.08
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.71
Var: Residual	214.38

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 119. PRISM: Culture values (TradAgg + SurvSAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ cob_TradAgg * cob_SurvSAgg + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	13.25 [9.47; 17.04]*
cob_TradAgg	-0.07 [-1.72; 1.58]
cob_SurvSAgg	-0.30 [-1.43; 0.83]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.22; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.97 [1.11; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.28 [-3.81; 1.24]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.97 [-1.79; 3.74]
cob_TradAgg:cob_SurvSAgg	0.67 [-0.52; 1.85]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.42
AIC	59501.93
BIC	59584.20
Log Likelihood	-29738.97
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	139.87
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.08
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.67
Var: Residual	214.39

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 120. PRISM: Culture values (TradAgg * SurvSAgg) (LMM)

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cob_TradAgg + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	15.27 [11.34; 19.21]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	1.92 [-1.02; 4.86]
rater_ethnicityBlack / African	-2.58 [-5.48; 0.33]
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino	2.02 [-0.92; 4.97]
rater_ethnicityIndigenous / First Peoples	-12.14 [-21.43; -2.85]*
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern / Arab	-2.25 [-9.86; 5.35]
rater_ethnicityMixed	-2.09 [-5.50; 1.32]
rater_age_groupboomer	-1.20 [-4.32; 1.91]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.89 [-0.94; 2.73]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.92 [-1.07; 2.92]
rater_genderFemale	-3.17 [-4.67; -1.68]*
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender	-4.00 [-10.41; 2.41]
cob_TradAgg	0.15 [-1.20; 1.50]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.07 [5.21; 6.93]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.97 [1.11; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.79 [-4.32; 0.75]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.11 [-2.75; 2.97]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.03
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	59452.21
BIC	59596.18
Log Likelihood	-29705.11
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	136.00
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.06
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.54
Var: Residual	214.38

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 122. PRISM: Demographics + selected culture-values additive (trad) (LMM)

	harmful ~ cob_quadrant + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	13.61 [10.06; 17.15]*
cob_quadrantII	1.08 [-1.61; 3.77]
cob_quadrantIII	0.94 [-2.77; 4.64]
cob_quadrantIV	-0.57 [-2.71; 1.57]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.21; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.96 [1.11; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.53 [-4.03; 0.97]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.67 [-2.06; 3.39]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.02
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.42
AIC	59496.59
BIC	59578.86
Log Likelihood	-29736.29
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	139.93
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.08
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.71
Var: Residual	214.38

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: cob_quadrant = I; conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 125. PRISM: Culture quadrants (LMM)

Quantifying the Salience of Geo-Cultural Values for Pluralistic Safety Alignment

	harmful ~ ethnicity + age + gender + cob_quadrant + conv_type + lm_fam + (1 rater_id) + (1 llm_provider/llm)
(Intercept)	15.35 [11.53; 19.17]*
rater_ethnicityAsian	1.63 [-1.44; 4.71]
rater_ethnicityBlack / African	-3.02 [-6.14; 0.09]
rater_ethnicityHispanic / Latino	1.81 [-1.29; 4.91]
rater_ethnicityIndigenous / First Peoples	-12.11 [-21.40; -2.81]*
rater_ethnicityMiddle Eastern / Arab	-2.28 [-9.89; 5.33]
rater_ethnicityMixed	-2.16 [-5.56; 1.24]
rater_age_groupboomer	-1.24 [-4.36; 1.89]
rater_age_groupgenx	0.83 [-1.02; 2.68]
rater_age_groupgenz	0.93 [-1.08; 2.93]
rater_genderFemale	-3.18 [-4.68; -1.67]*
rater_genderNon-binary / third gender	-3.95 [-10.36; 2.47]
cob_quadrantII	0.03 [-2.98; 3.05]
cob_quadrantIII	1.26 [-2.75; 5.27]
cob_quadrantIV	0.15 [-2.42; 2.72]
conversation_typecontroversy guided	6.08 [5.21; 6.94]*
conversation_typevalues guided	1.97 [1.12; 2.82]*
lm_familiaritySomewhat familiar	-1.78 [-4.31; 0.76]
lm_familiarityVery familiar	0.07 [-2.77; 2.92]
R_m^2 (theoretical)	0.03
R_c^2 (theoretical)	0.43
AIC	59448.77
BIC	59606.45
Log Likelihood	-29701.39
Num. obs.	7014
Num. groups: rater_id	1279
Num. groups: llm:llm_provider	21
Num. groups: llm_provider	6
Var: rater_id (Intercept)	136.22
Var: llm:llm_provider (Intercept)	0.06
Var: llm_provider (Intercept)	10.53
Var: Residual	214.38

* 0 outside the confidence interval. Reference levels: rater_ethnicity = White; rater_age_group = millennial; rater_gender = Male; cob_quadrant = I; conversation_type = unguided; lm_familiarity = Not familiar at all.

Table 126. PRISM: Demographics + Quadrants additive (LMM)